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English Medium Instruction at the University of Chittagong: A Case Study

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis is based on my original research under the supervision of Mr. Ibrahim Hosssain, Associate Professor, Institute of Modern Languages, University of Chittagong. I have not submitted this thesis for any degree elsewhere. This thesis does not include any previously published or written material unless properly cited through accurate referencing.

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the current situation of implementing English as a medium of instruction (EMI) at the University of Chittagong in Bangladesh, with a view to identifying the challenges faced by its stakeholders (teachers and students mostly who shift from Bangla medium instruction to EMI), its impact on students, and recommending possible solutions. It followed a mixed-method approach and employed questionnaires and classroom observations as data collection tools. Data were collected from 180 students and 8 teachers from various disciplines participating in EMI programs at the university. The study revealed that while students and teachers perceived EMI as a beneficial initiative for enhancing global competitiveness and English proficiency, several challenges hindered its implementation. These included students' varying levels of English language proficiency, psychological barriers such as anxiety and fear of judgment, lack of preparatory language courses, insufficient teacher training, and institutional support. The study recommended the inclusion of tailored preparatory English courses, teacher training programs focused on EMI pedagogy, and structured policy frameworks for improving the success of EMI at public universities in Bangladesh.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

English, a member of the Indo-European language family, is now the most widely spoken language in the world, with approximately 1.5 billion speakers. Originating in England, this language started to spread its roots during the 17th century through colonialism. Since then, even after the end of colonialism, it has retained its status in many countries it once ruled and gained the status of an official language in countries like India, Singapore, and many others. Even in countries where English is not an official language, it is often regarded as the primary choice for a foreign language. In developing countries like Bangladesh, it is still considered as the language of the elites. Proficiency in English opens doors to a lot of opportunities. Hence, significant emphasis is placed on learning this language.

In Bangladesh, students start to learn English as a compulsory subject at the age of 7, and English is given 200 marks in the SSC and HSC exams, two significant public exams for the country's students. Yet, most students in Bangladesh fail to achieve the expected English proficiency due to factors such as resource shortages, teachers' inability to teach English effectively, and a lack of willingness to implement CLT¹ policies adopted by The Ministry of Education of Bangladesh. Many universities are currently adopting globally trending English-medium instruction (EMI) to tackle this issue. EMI tries to help students improve their English proficiency while studying their subject content. However, there are also challenges in EMI that need to be addressed.

This initial chapter explains the study's justification by providing its background, aims, objec-

¹CLT or Communicative Language Teaching is an approach that aims to develop English speaking fluency first and foremost.

tives, and significance. It also presents the research questions and outlines the structure of the dissertation.

1.1 Research Background

The growing importance of English as a global language has created a socio-cultural, educational, and political impact (Phillipson, 2004). Tsuda (1994) described it as a medium for internationalization, globalization, academia, and scientific advancement. This reputation of English has given rise to the expansion of English Medium Instruction (EMI) all around the world (Julie Dearden, 2014; Ernesto Macaro, 2018). English as an MOI aligns with globalization as English proficiency opens up a gateway for high-skilled job sectors and international mobility (Gibbins, 2023).

The medium of instruction (MOI) refers to the language teachers use for teaching. It significantly influences students' academic performance and plays an important role in their linguistic and cultural identity, particularly in multilingual settings (Evans & Morrison, 2011). An example of MOI can be if an institution implements Arabic as the primary language from the very beginning of the program. This implementation may help the students to be fluent in the Arabic language and also be good at the subject matter. MOI can empower students by offering them access to global knowledge, but it can also create a barrier that may hamper students' academic performance and sense of belonging.

English Medium Instruction (EMI) refers to using English as the medium for transmitting academic knowledge, irrespective of the first language of students or teachers, to simultaneously improve linguistic and academic competencies (Aguilar & Muñoz, 2014). EMI has gained prominence in recent years because of globalization, as educational institutions aim to prepare students with the language and academic skills needed to engage in an increasingly interconnected world (Ernesto Macaro, 2015).

The concept of EMI dates back to the time of colonization. English was introduced during this time in several places. English became the primary administrative language of the British Empire. They established English as a language of power and prestige, and thus, they integrated English into the formal education systems of these regions (Edwards, 2024).

In order to establish a class of English-educated elites who could support the administration of British colonial power, English was introduced into the education system of higher education in the Indian subcontinent (Md. M Rahman & Singh, 2020). In this context, Thomas Babington Macaulay's 1835 "Minutes on Indian Education" is significant. Macaulay believed that educating Indians in English would serve their purpose of creating Indians who would be loyal to the British empire, a class of people Indian in blood and color but English in tastes, opinions, morals, and intellect (Macaulay, 1835).

After decolonization in the mid-20s, English retained its significance in many former colonial countries, including Bangladesh, even after its independence in 1971 (Ahmed & M. R. Islam, 2019). In the following decades, English remained important in many countries due to the global rise of English in scientific research, multinational cooperation, and the expansion of the Internet. As globalization intensified, proficiency in English became a valuable skill that opened the door to international trade, diplomacy, education, and employment. The recent spread of EMI can be seen as a continuation of the historical trends mentioned and a motivation shaped by the global economy. Thus, English has become the world's lingua franca (Ahmed & M. R. Islam, 2019).

1.1.1 Current EMI Scenario

In today's interconnected world, educational institutions are implementing English as their MOI to prepare their students for global competition and participation in international academic and professional networks. Many countries are now gradually introducing EMI in their education system, identifying EMI as a gateway to scientific knowledge, technology, research, and academic opportunities (Ahmed & M. R. Islam, 2019).

EMI aims to improve students' English language skills and, at the same time, teach academic knowledge. The goal is to produce students who are not only good at their field but also proficient in English (Galloway, 2023). EMI is also viewed as a strategy for internationalizing higher education so that students who have taken English as their medium of instruction can be able to collaborate with foreign institutions and research.

The implementation of EMI comes with various challenges. Students who shift to EMI from other mediums of instruction face inequalities as students with strong English skills get advantages over students who do not have strong English skills. This trend can be even

more noticeable in an EMI classroom where all the students come from diverse backgrounds. Moreover, many previous studies found that teachers may lack the necessary training to deliver lectures effectively in English, leading to a drop in teaching ability.

1.1.2 EMI Scenario in Bangladesh

Bangladesh currently has three mediums of instruction: English, Arabic, and Bangla. Because of its colonial past, the nation has a high preference for English apart from its first language (L1). Bangla was prioritized over English after its independence as a reflection of nationalism; however, subsequent socio-economic changes reinstated English to its former prominence. Now, English enjoys the status of being the most prestigious foreign language in Bangladesh (Akter & S. M. Mitul, 2020). EMI was introduced in Bangladeshi tertiary education after the enactment of the 1992 Private University Act (A. Kabir & Webb, 2018). EMI is currently being used in several public and private universities in Bangladesh. The middle and upper socioeconomic people have viewed EMI as a more significant MOI than other MOIs since its beginning (R. Chowdhury & A. H. Kabir, 2014).

However, Bangladesh does not have a defined language policy (LP) or even a language in education policy (R. Faquire, 2019). As a result, the implementation of EMI is now completely unregulated in Bangladesh. Most students and teachers who enroll in these universities are from colleges and schools that use the Bangla language as their medium of instruction.

1.1.3 EMI at The University of Chittagong

The University of Chittagong is one of the leading public universities in Bangladesh. In this university, Bangla is the predominant medium of instruction. It has implemented EMI in some departments and institutions in response to globalization and the increasing demand for English proficiency. However, there is no specific formal policy guideline for the implementation of EMI that has been developed centrally. Moreover, there is no specific assessment to evaluate students' English proficiency, which can help teachers plan their curriculum according to students' overall proficiency and comprehension. Instead, students are required to take an admission test for university entry, which includes an English assessment section that is inadequate to evaluate students' level of proficiency in English. Also, most of the teachers come from non-English

backgrounds, which further complicates the situation. Hence, teachers and students have to navigate a system that is not fully equipped to meet their needs. All these underscore the need for a structured policy to support EMI at the University of Chittagong.

Although English-medium instruction is not new in Bangladesh, and many schools, colleges, and private universities in Bangladesh offer English as their sole medium of instruction, the history of EMI in the public universities of Bangladesh is significantly new. While English-medium schools, colleges, and private universities can be prohibitively expensive for middle-class Bangladeshis, public universities are much cheaper and more affordable than those for most of the middle to lower-class people of Bangladesh. In private English-medium schools, colleges, and universities, where most students come from elite socioeconomic classes and enjoy a privileged academic life, most students in public universities typically do not enjoy the same privileges due to their prior educational background. This results in an unequal learning environment, and it becomes more challenging for students if their discipline offers only English medium of instruction. In Bangladeshi government schools and colleges where these students study, teachers generally focus on preparing students to get good marks in English exams rather than building a solid foundation in grammar, which results in most students lacking proficiency in English. After being accepted to the university, Students often feel a sense of excitement about EMI because of the social prestige associated with it, viewing English as a prestigious medium of instruction and recognizing its global significance for future career opportunities. However, as the academic year progresses, they begin to face the challenges of EMI. They have to deal with dual challenges: the pressure of higher studies and the pressure of learning their content matter through English. They are also required to give class assessments such as presentations, CTs, assignments, and everything else in English. They seem to feel overwhelmed, and they lose interest in studying and attending to the classroom due to the fear of being judged by their teachers or peers due to their lack of English proficiency. Together, these factors significantly affect students' social lives and mental health.

EMI aims for more than outstanding grades; it wants students to be proficient in English as well. So the questions arise: Are students able to improve their English performance over

the course of four years? What is the condition of their academic results? Are they able to understand their subject matter in the English language, or are they only improving their academic results by following rote memorization? If yes, then a big question arises as to whether EMI implementation at the universities is a failure.

As a stakeholder, I have faced these challenges as well, including difficulties with academic content in English and the pressure of maintaining grades. This study is motivated by the challenges I as a stakeholder faced and my experiences with the EMI program.

1.2 Aims & Objectives of the Research

The University of Chittagong is still in the initial phase of EMI implementation. With the EMI craze ongoing, this research aims to provide an overall EMI scenario at the University of Chittagong and investigate the challenges students and teachers face in the EMI program.

This study first explores students' educational backgrounds, such as the areas where they completed their SSC or HSC and their prior medium of instruction, to maintain the inclusive diversity of students and to find out if their prior experiences influence their EMI experience, adaptability, performance, and language proficiency.

This study then investigates students' perceptions of EMI, whether they find it promising or challenging, by asking them to rate their overall experience of EMI and also by asking them about its impact on their academic performance. To understand the challenges faced by students in the EMI program, this study explores the perception of students about their classroom experience and explores their psychological barriers, such as anxiety and fear of judgment while using English in the classroom.

EMI programs generally offer preparatory English language courses for first-year students. This study examines the sufficiency of the course by inquiring whether students think their GED Functional Language course or Preparatory English language course is sufficient to meet their needs.

This study also inquires about the academic performance trends of the students from their first to fourth year, which will shed light on the influence of EMI on students' academic performance. Additionally, students' coping mechanisms and academic assessment quality were investigated to determine whether students' academic performance correlates more strongly with EMI policy

or students' own effort.

Finally, this study examines students' self-assessed English proficiency and readiness for job opportunities requiring English proficiency. It seeks to determine whether the EMI program succeeded in improving students' academic knowledge and proficiency in the English language, thus preparing them for global academic and professional opportunities (Galloway & Richard Ruegg, 2020; Ernesto Macaro, 2018).

For teachers, this study aims to assess how well their educational backgrounds and experiences enable them to conduct an entire English immersion class. The study also examines teachers' language preferences and comfort levels in participating in entirely immersive English classes to understand the teachers' role in the current situation of EMI programs from their perspective.

Teacher training programs and institutional support are crucial for the EMI program to be successful, so this study investigates if the teachers of this university get proper training for the EMI program and how important it is in their opinion. This investigation can help us check the institutional support situation and give recommendations for EMI policymaking.

Classroom interaction, engagement, and feedback are also crucial for EMI implementation. This study investigates whether teachers engage with students in the classroom and practice collecting feedback from students so that they can tailor their lectures based on their feedback. Furthermore, this study seeks opinions regarding their reluctance to fully engage in English-medium instruction to understand their perceptions of the challenges in effectively delivering English Medium Instruction (EMI).

Together, these aims and objectives will sum up an overview of the EMI program at the University of Chittagong (CU), its impact on students' academic performance, and the challenges that teachers and students face in the program.

1.3 Research Questions

RQ 1: How does English Medium Instruction (EMI) impact the academic performance and English proficiency of students who shift from other mediums of instruction to EMI at the University of Chittagong?

RQ 2: What challenges do students and teachers face in an EMI environment at the University of Chittagong?

1.4 Significance

A significant number of research has been conducted on EMI, but most of these studies are based on the European context. Some research on EMI has been conducted in Bangladesh, but the majority of these studies primarily focus on EMI in private universities. While a study by Akter & S. M. Mitul (2020) on the EMI situation at Bangladesh University of Professionals (BUP) indicated that the university is a public institution, it does not conform to the characteristics of a typical public university. BUP's website describes it as a "unique public university" run by the Bangladesh Army. Apart from individuals with military family ties, most students who attend this university are from the upper echelons of society and have a solid command of English because of the higher tuition costs and special admissions standards. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first research on the EMI situation at a typical public university in Bangladesh, which attracts students from all socioeconomic classes, primarily middle- and lower-middle-class ones.

The present study attempts to address the existing research gaps. This result is significant for students who are currently studying in EMI or who have just shifted from other mediums of instruction to English medium instruction. The study demonstrates the challenges that students with low English proficiency face in an English Medium Instruction setting, particularly during their first year. The study addresses challenges such as language barriers, anxiety, fear of judgment, lack of confidence among students, and the extra effort required to master both the subject matter and language in an EMI setting. The study also proposes suggestions to implement preparatory English courses or enhance the existing GED courses to help students adapt to the EMI environment. The study examines the factors contributing to the challenges many students face in achieving academic success and average classroom outcomes during their first year. The discussion then focuses on the coping mechanisms students use to adjust to their new environment and how these strategies improve their academic performance. This study emphasizes the significance of classroom engagement and support in addressing the challenges encountered in EMI.

The study highlights the challenges teachers face in delivering lectures in an EMI setting. This study is significant for teachers as it encourages a tailored teaching program and highlights students' expectations from EMI classrooms. This understanding may help teachers in creating a more engaging and supportive classroom environment.

This study is significant for policymakers as it advocates for a strong EMI policy. This study provides valuable insights that may assist policymakers in designing an effective EMI framework for the University of Chittagong and other public universities.

1.5 Dissertation Structure

The dissertation is divided into five chapters, each focusing on a specific aspect of the study:

Chapter 1: Introduction explains the study's justification by providing its background, aims, objectives, and significance. It also presents the research questions and outlines the structure of the dissertation.

Chapter 2: Literature Review provides the relevant literature by presenting an overview of EMI as a concept, its historical context, and the challenges that may come with EMI implementation. This chapter also offers an overview of recent studies on EMI, identifying existing literature gaps and future directions.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology outlines the study's research methodology, including the research design, sampling, data collection, and data analysis, as well as ethical considerations.

Chapter 4: Findings and Data Analysis presents the findings of the statistical and qualitative analyses of the data collected for this study, which aim to answer the research questions.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusion summarizes and discusses the study's key findings; it then concludes by presenting answers to the research questions, policy recommendations, and limitations of the study and offering suggestions for future research directions.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter elucidates the relevant literature by presenting an overview of English Medium Instruction (EMI) as a concept, a global trend, and its historical context. It also examines the implementation of EMI, its challenges, and the support mechanisms that are important for a successful EMI program. This chapter concludes with an overview of recent studies on EMI, identifying existing literature gaps and future directions.

2.1 English Medium Instruction (EMI)

English Medium Instruction is the practice of conducting instruction in English, even in contexts where English is not widely spoken outside the classroom (Jenkins & Mauranen, 2019). In other words, it is the use of English to teach academic content in countries where the first language (L1) is not English (Julie Dearden, 2014). EMI is used in teaching non-linguistic academic subjects like law, Environmental science, Computer Engineering, etc., in non-English-speaking countries (Ernesto Macaro, 2018). Dafouz & Smit (2016) characterized it as the usage of English as the primary medium of instruction in multilingual educational settings. In China's higher education context Hu & Lei (2014) defined EMI as a method where English is used to enhance students' English proficiency and improve the university's global position. However, they also mentioned that EMI's effectiveness depends on the language proficiency of both students and teachers. EMI has become an essential strategy for the global education system due to globalization and the influence of economic, social, and academic perspectives (Altbach & Knight, 2007). It has become the universal second language and now works as a global lingua franca (Fishman, 2000).

In the current global order of languages, the role of the English language is very significant (Zhang, 2017). EMI prepares students for a globalized workforce and attracts international students to higher education institutions (Wächter & Maiworm, 2014). That is why universities around the world are adopting EMI to enhance students' English proficiency, improve global competitiveness, and meet the demand for a globalized educational landscape (Julie Dearden, 2014; Ernesto Macaro, 2018). Galloway & Richard Ruegg (2020) described EMI as a framework designed to improve educational accessibility for international students and prepare graduates for global employment opportunities.

Different approaches, such as ELT, CBLT, and EMI, are used to implement English in the education system. The main focus of ELT is language learning, whereas EMI mainly focuses on teaching content using the English language (Ernesto Macaro, Curle, et al., 2018). It primarily prioritizes mastery in academic content with no direct intention of improving student's English ability (Julie Dearden & Ernesto Macaro, 2016) and it is expected that language development is to occur incidentally throughout content learning (Taguchi, 2014).

2.1.1 History of EMI

As English has become the universal second language of higher education, EMI has become a significant trend in higher studies worldwide (Brumfit, 2004). Many universities in non-English speaking countries are now implementing EMI to attract international students and to improve local students' employability (Mohammad O. Hamid et al., 2013). The 1999 Bologna declaration helped EMI to gain its prominence (Brown & Annette Bradford, 2017). This declaration aimed to standardize European higher education to enhance academic mobility and employability. After the Bologna declaration, EMI gained momentum worldwide, leading to the widespread incorporation of English in tertiary education in non-English speaking countries (Walkinshaw & Duong, 2017). From 2001 to 2004, the number of EMI programs in Europe grew more than tenfold, which showcases the global trends toward rapid EMI expansion (Maiworm & Wachter, 2002; Wachter & Maiworm, 2008). Many European and Asian countries are now adopting EMI at a high rate due to globalization and growing demand for English proficiency in the job sector (Coleman, 2006). Within the South Asian context, countries like Bangladesh are gradually increasing the implementation of EMI to develop linguistic competence to align with

the international standard (Md. M Rahman & Singh, 2020). Studies conducted by Evans & Morrison (2017), and M. O. Hamid, I. Jahan & M. M. Islam (2013) also affirm this statement. Other derivatives of EMI implementations in these countries are the motivation to familiarize students with the increasing status of English as a lingua franca and the institutional derive for internationalization through the 'Englishisation' of curricula (Galloway & Mckinley, 2021). Factors like policy context and institutional goals also play a great role in EMI implementation across global, regional, national, and local levels (Hultgren et al., 2015).

In Asia, EMI expansion in higher education is related to regional agreements like the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) and national initiatives like China's Project 1985 and Vietnam's National Foreign Language Projects (Humphreys et al., 2017; Zhou & Heath Rose, 2021).

In the Indian subcontinent, a land with nearly 580 distinct dialects (Grierson, 1928), we can trace EMI roots back to the colonial period when The British Empire introduced English in the education system to train a local elite class in British administrative and educational standards (Tariq Rahman, 1999). Over time, English has become a symbol of socioeconomic advancement, especially in higher education and specialized sectors (Proctor, 2017). Even after the post-colonial era, English has retained its top position in the linguistic hierarchy in this subcontinent, primarily due to its association with social elitism and power (M. Hamid & Iffat Jahan, 2015).

In recent decades, countries like Bangladesh, India, Sri Lanka, and Pakistan have gradually introduced EMI to their tertiary educational systems and even, in some contexts, to secondary and higher secondary levels to improve employability and align with the global academic standard (M. O. Hamid, I. Jahan & M. Islam, 2013).

2.1.2 History of English & EMI in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, "Bangla is the de facto and de jure national language" (Banu & Sussex, 2001). But from the British colonial period to the present, English has always been the most prestigious foreign language (Akter & S. M. Mitul, 2020) here. After the partition of the Indian subcontinent, between 1947 and 1971, English enjoyed great prestige in East Pakistan society as an official language and the primary communication tool (Tariq Rahman, 1996). In 1971, Bangladesh

emerged as a sovereign country. At that time, due to the strong national sentiment, Bangla was given the status of national language by an amendment to the constitution in 1972 and instructed to be used in education, administration, and jurisdiction (Tariq Rahman, 1999). Later, The Bengali Introduction Law of 1987 clarified that Bangla would be used in all spheres and levels for government purposes (Banu & Sussex, 2001). This law made it compulsory for higher education to be conducted in Bangla even though resources were insufficient in the national language (Choudhury, 2001).

As the fervor of nationalism began to decline, it was then realized that restoring English to its rightful place was necessary. This was followed by a report by the Bangladesh Education Extension and Research Institute (BEERI), stating that most students are not achieving satisfactory proficiency levels compared to the syllabus and textbooks in use (BEERI, 1976; M. Hamid & Erling, 2016). English was then introduced as a compulsory subject in the first grade in 1991 and reintroduced as a compulsory course at the tertiary level (Md. Obaidul Hamid & Jr., 2008).

From the 1990s onward, Bangladesh has observed a positive move towards the English language Education Policy (ELEP) due to the necessity of keeping pace with globalization (Nur et al., 2020). The move in favor of English gained momentum when the Government of Bangladesh passed the “Private University Act 1992” to meet the increasing demand for tertiary education. After the promulgation of this act, the number of private universities has grown dramatically (M. M. Islam, 2013). This act encourages the learning of English at the tertiary level (M. M. Rahman, 2015). Since then, all private universities in Bangladesh have adopted English as their primary medium of instruction (Sharkar, 2019). No private universities in Bangladesh offer any non-linguistic courses in Bangla, and they identify themselves as English medium universities on their websites (Md. M Rahman & Singh, 2020). However, they still don’t have any specific policy regarding EMI in the Private University Act, which again was revised in 2010 (M. Rahman & Mehar Singh, 2019).

To align with globalization trends, public universities in Bangladesh are lately implementing English Medium Instruction (EMI) in their educational systems (Akter & S. M. Mitul, 2020). However, unlike private universities, this implementation of EMI is employed only in specific departments in public universities. It is generally expected that code-switching and interlingual lectures are used in public universities of Bangladesh (M. O. Hamid, I. Jahan & M. Islam, 2013).

2.2 Implementation of EMI

EMI is now implemented in academic curricula worldwide due to the need for English proficiency for graduate employability (Costa & Coleman, 2013). Lately, English competence is expected to be an outcome requirement for fresh graduates (Tri & Moskovsky, 2019). Because of its sensation, EMI is now described as “an unstoppable train in tertiary-level education” (Ernesto Macaro, 2017). Europe was the first to implement EMI in its education system. A study by the Academic Cooperation Association (APC) found that around 2400 courses were offered in English in European countries (Wachter & Maiworm, 2008), and the percentage of postgraduate students taking courses in English rose to 44% (Collins & Halverson, 2009). Universities are increasingly incorporating the English language as their medium of instruction in many disciplines and their curriculum (Yuan et al., 2020). Following this global trend of EMI in tertiary education, many non-Anglophone countries around the globe are now transforming their educational programs into English as an alternative to the native language (Shimauchi, 2018). Many Asian countries are no different; they also have implemented English Medium Instruction in their academic systems and observe EMI with prominence and significance (Galloway, Numajiri & Rees, 2020; Naun, 2003). South Korea, Japan, and China updated their higher education by introducing English as a medium of instruction to their education system due to its popularity, global reputation, and association with power and prestige (Lassegard, 2006; Tsuneyoshi, 2005). South Asian countries that were part of the British Empire, such as India, Malaysia, Hong Kong, and Singapore, have also widely implemented EMI in their education systems (Altbach, 2004; Balla & Penning, 1996). India, one of the largest multilingual nations, has a significant English-speaking population. It has led to a high level of comfort with the language due to the necessity of communicating with a vast array of linguistic groups (M. M. Islam, 2013). However, this language situation differs in Bangladesh, where the scope for practicing English is very narrow and is generally used by elite-class people in daily conversation by code-switching¹.

Bangladesh, a South Asian country with a colonial past, declared Bangla its national language in 1972. It has a 98 % Bangla-speaking population who use Bangla from education to jurisdiction

¹Code-switching is when a speaker alternates between two or more languages.

(Shah et al., 2022). In this country, English is regarded as the mark of sophistication and a stepping stone to success (Hossain, 2013). It was introduced by Bangladesh's government as a required course in the National Education Policy (NEP) in 1992; EMI in tertiary education was instituted by the Private University Act that same year (R. K. Faquire, 2021). Since its introduction, EMI has received strong support from upper-echelon individuals who favor English for its prestige, academic usage, and role in social mobility (Unterhalter et al., 2003).

2.2.1 Challenges and Issues in EMI Implementation

Despite its significant popularity and worldwide demand, English Medium Instruction (EMI) is not without its criticisms. It presents many challenges and issues that need to be addressed. One of the significant challenges in EMI classrooms is the difficulty that students with low English proficiency face in engaging in class discussions, understanding lectures, and completing assignments (Hung & Lan, 2017). Not all students admitted to EMI classrooms possess proficiency in the English language; many students entering EMI at the tertiary level come from different mediums of instruction. Their diverse backgrounds and prior education lead to linguistic and cultural challenges, impacting their engagement in EMI settings. This results in a division in the classroom among students who are proficient in English (Akter & M. Mitul, 2020). The students with lower English proficiency experience feelings of alienation and often remain silent during class discussions, which contributes to their sense of isolation and reluctance to engage in the classroom (R. Sultana, 2018). A study by Sarkar et al. (2021) found that students encounter challenges in actively participating in English due to anxiety and limited language skills, which result in a lack of motivation and self-esteem. Another challenge these students face in the classroom is the fear of being judged by others, which leads to hesitation in asking questions and engaging in classroom discussions in English (H. Rahman & Kaur, 2018). Higher-level courses require critical thinking, academic discussion, debate, and analysis. However, due to self-doubt and disengagement in EMI classrooms, students with lower proficiency in English face significant challenges in higher education, often experiencing what Graddol (2010) describes as a 'double burden' in mastering their subject rather than a 'double gain' from EMI programs (Ernesto Macaro, 2017).

Teachers in EMI classes may sometimes overlook linguistic components, as they believe

that language instruction is not within their teaching responsibilities or even within their expertise (Block & Moncada-Comas, 2022; J. Dearden & E. Macaro, 2016). If English is not the teachers' native language, then they tend to face difficulties in effectively delivering complex subject matter in English (Ernesto Macaro & Han, 2020). The study by Ernesto Macaro & Han (2020) also found that teachers in EMI settings frequently lack pedagogical skills suited for EMI, and along with their insufficient English proficiency, this may result in instructional difficulties. Another significant issue for teachers in the EMI context is the necessity to create and share content in English, especially for those whose native language (L1) is not English. This additional pressure can contribute to potential burnout (Annemarie Bradford, 2016). Due to their lack of sufficient proficiency in English to teach course content and/or to help students understand complex concepts, teachers often resort to code-switching. Although helpful, it may compromise the EMI policy and reveal a gap in language support policy (M. M. Rahman et al., 2019; Zenkova & Khamitova, 2017).

In countries such as Bangladesh, EMI implementation in higher education is driven by the economic and strategic advantages of the English language. Some perceive EMI as a type of linguistic imperialism, expressing concern about its effects on native languages and cultures, especially the fear of undermining local languages such as Bangla (H. Rahman & Kaur, 2018). This cultural resistance can further hinder EMI implementation (Julie Dearden & Ernesto Macaro, 2016). For non-native Anglophone countries, many instructional materials in the EMI program are imported from the European context, which is contextually irrelevant to the students. This may hinder comprehension ability for students who are unfamiliar with foreign examples and case studies. Teachers face difficulties in finding EMI-compatible resources, especially those that relate to local contexts. This limits students' ability to connect with the resource (Akter & M. Mitul, 2020). Teachers try to contextualize these resources, but it requires additional time and effort. EMI programs also include specialized language courses aimed at improving students' academic skills. However, the expected outcome is often unmet, resulting in struggles with understanding and producing academic English, particularly in discipline-specific contexts. The duration of these courses is limited, which usually fails to prepare students well enough for EMI requirements, and teachers report that students still have trouble with language skills after completing their initial language courses (Pham, 2023). Ibrahim (2001) pointed out that EMI is

unlikely to equitably improve the four language skills (Listening, Reading, Writing, Speaking) for both teachers and students. Another issue that Pham (2023) highlighted in his study is that EMI programs often do not have rigorous language assessments and evaluations to ensure students have the necessary skills for EMI courses. In many cases, EMI programs also lack institutional support for professional development (Ernesto Macaro, Akincioglu & Han, 2019). The lack of adequate training programs along with proper institutional support and resources for teachers and students undermine EMI implementations and jeopardizes its sustainability (Akter & M. Mitul, 2020). M. M. Rahman et al. (2019), in his study, found that there is often a disconnection between EMI policy and its practical implementation in countries like Bangladesh, where English is not the L1; they further stated that policymakers often overlook the specific needs and structure of EMI programs. EMI can be both beneficial and detrimental to students' academic careers. While some studies report improvements in students' language proficiency, many studies also show evidence of an impact on students' academic performance. The mixed evidence has led to the need for EMI policies that are more context-sensitive, aiming to balance content and language goals.

2.2.2 Students and Teachers' Perceptions of EMI

Some studies indicate that EMI enhances students' English proficiency over time (Galloway & Rachael Ruegg, 2020), while others show that EMI may impact students' comprehension of complex academic content if they lack enough English skills (Airey & Linder, 2006). Studies in Thailand and Japan show that students face difficulties in STEM subjects due to the added complexity of English instruction (Aizawa & H. Rose, 2019; Jomdech et al., 2024). One of the reasons contributing to this challenge could be students' inability to take notes in the classroom due to the complexity of this non-native language (Annemarie Bradford, 2016). They are used to being in a native language classroom setting; as a result, it becomes harder for them if their lectures are solely given in English. M. M. Rahman et al. (2019) found that many students who come from non-English backgrounds find written assignments and exams challenging, especially those who have limited English writing skills. Hence, their academic result was greatly hampered, especially in their first year. Due to all these mixed outcomes of EMI, students' and teachers' perceptions regarding EMI vary. Some students view EMI as an opportunity through

which they can improve their English proficiency along with their discipline courses, but others feel disadvantages due to language barriers that may come with EMI (Airey, 2011). Teachers also expressed mixed attitudes towards EMI. Some view EMI as a means to improve their language and teaching skills and match their skills with international standards (Kirkpatrick, 2014) while others feel the exact opposite and consider it a burden (Ernesto Macaro, Curle, et al., 2018), and a challenge to accommodate diverse English proficiency levels at the EMI classroom (Ernesto Macaro & Han, 2020). Akter & M. Mitul (2020) reported that teachers often feel pressured to switch between English and the local language to aid students in understanding complex topics. Although institutions implement a strict English-only policy in their EMI programs, these teachers believe that code-switching can help reduce linguistic barriers in the classroom (M. M. Rahman et al., 2019).

Even with all the mixed perceptions regarding EMI, students and teachers recognize the economic value that proficiency in English brings (Costales, 2017). That is why most of the students while finding EMI challenging, take this challenge as a means through which they can improve their English skills in the long run. This notion of viewing the challenges as beneficial for the future is often echoed by teachers who also agree that exposure to EMI builds students' English proficiency over time (Zumor & Qasem, 2019).

2.2.3 Support Mechanisms for EMI Success

Researchers have proposed various support mechanisms to deal with the challenges inherent in EMI. Evans & Green (2007) suggested implementing preparatory English courses at the beginning of the EMI program. Nur et al. (2020) also emphasized this aspect, but they also proposed that the institution should redesign these English courses to address specific needs in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These courses can significantly help students with non-English backgrounds. Teacher training is equally important for the EMI program as studies have shown that professional development programs focused on language and teaching can greatly improve teaching effectiveness (Wächter & Maiworm, 2014). (Akter & S. M. Mitul, 2020) suggested strategically using students' native language in EMI programs, e.g., controlled code-switching and translanguaging, which can aid students' comprehension. They also add that institutes should include training sessions and policy guidance so that code-switching

and translanguaging can improve students' comprehension without compromising the goals of EMI. These will allow teachers to balance the EMI English-only policy with native language assistance for students with low English proficiency. M. M. Rahman et al. (2019) suggested that institutions should offer Non-credit, specialized courses for students who need extra support for specific language areas, and teachers should assess students' weaknesses to offer them support. Establishing writing labs, debating clubs, and language clubs, and introducing programs such as Student Teaching Student (STS), where higher-performing students help their peers, can also help low-performing students gain language proficiency in a collaborative setting (Akter & S. M. Mitul, 2020). To help students overcome the fear of judgment and build confidence R. Sultana (2018) suggested that institutions should provide counseling and psychological support for students who feel anxious about using English. Overall, a national-level comprehensive language policy and a framework for evaluating students' English competency levels can help EMI implementation fully achieve its goals and ensure sustainable success (R. Faquire, 2019).

2.3 Review of Recent Literature

Recently, many studies have been conducted on EMI, which give us information about its current state and how well it works in different situations. These studies looked at the EMI's effects on students' language skills, academic success, and involvement, as well as its effects on society and culture as a whole. Institutional support was very important for the success of EMI, as shown by studies from universities in Europe and Asia. Some researchers, including Aguilar & Muñoz (2014), found that schools that provide intensive language aid to their students and training programs to their teachers have much higher success rates than schools without these kinds of facilities.

The main focus of EMI research has generally been on its impact on students' language proficiency and academic achievement. T. Rahman et al. (2019) showed that Bengali-medium students in Bangladesh face difficulties in understanding English and engaging academically in EMI environments. This research highlights the need for additional language support to ensure equitable learning opportunities. Akter & M. Mitul (2020) identified limited resources and inadequate institutional support in private universities as major barriers to implementing EMI for students with low English proficiency. The study also found that teachers often code-switch

despite their proficiency, which is inconsistent with EMI's English immersion model.

Milon et al. (2017) highlighted the differences in educational institutions and teaching methods in Bangladesh. Bengali-medium institutions emphasize grammar memorization and translation, while English-medium institutions emphasize contextual practice. Their study identified deficiencies in teacher qualifications and lesson planning in Bengali-medium institutions, which undermine students' English proficiency.

Shah et al. (2022) investigated the linguistic barriers and lack of resources in implementing EMI, which increase teachers' workload and their reliance on code-switching. A. M. Chowdhury (2021) noted that the strict implementation of EMI in private universities creates discrimination for Bengali-medium students, which negatively affects academic performance and increases anxiety.

The challenges that teachers and students face in an EMI environment are a common topic of discussion in the literature. Shah et al. (2022) showed that the linguistic barriers and lack of resources in EMI increase teachers' stress and reduce their effectiveness. To cope with these challenges, teachers often teach in simplified ways or resort to code-switching, which hinders the main goal of EMI. Akter & M. Mitul (2020) noted that the implementation of EMI at Bangladesh University of Professionals (BUP) requires additional efforts to improve students' various skills, which creates stress in the academic process.

Ali & M. Obaidul Hamid (2014) has shown that teachers play a crucial role in implementing EMI. They adapt their language strategies to the needs of students. The study says that there should be clear rules and training for teachers on how to use bilingual methods. S. Sultana (2014), in her study on the social and cultural effects of EMI, said that using English too much in school can make children lose touch with their local culture and identity. The study suggests a balanced policy and suggests using both English and Bengali as a way to be more competitive on the world stage.

Rosca (2012) has noted that English-medium institutions while focusing on developing linguistic skills, neglect social and emotional learning. Obaidullah (2022) and M. Rahman & Mehar Singh (2019) have expressed concerns about the rapid growth of EMI implementation and its cultural hegemony implications. They say that EMI policies should make sure that both local and global cultures are represented.

A study by Hung (2020) found that students participating in EMI programs did not significantly improve their language skills compared to students who did not take part in EMI programs. However, Zenkova & Khamitova (2017) showed that learning a second language makes it harder to do well in school because it requires a lot of mental work. But studies from Turkey and Vietnam Hung & Lan (2017) and Köksal & Tercan (2019) have shown that EMI is a chance for students to build their confidence and speaking skills.

2.3.1 Literature Gaps and Future Direction

EMI is a widely researched topic, with ongoing studies conducted regularly, yet certain gaps remain. Contexts like society, place, stockholders' perception, institutions' expectations, and initiatives all play a role in EMI's effectiveness. Much of EMI's research is based on European contexts. In Asian contexts, especially in Bangladesh, more research on EMI is needed as public universities in Bangladesh are gradually implementing EMI in many of their disciplines, following Private universities. There is a lack of significant studies on students' coping mechanisms in EMI programs. Future research also has the scope to explore the role of technology, such as online resources, artificial intelligence (AI), and language learning apps, in supporting EMI.

This study investigates the EMI situation at a public university in Bangladesh and analyzes how students who come from other mediums of instruction are coping with this setting.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

This chapter outlines the study's research methodology, including the research design, sampling, data collection, and data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

A mixed methods research design was chosen to address the research questions for this study. Combining quantitative and qualitative methods provides a comprehensive analysis for the study (J. W. Creswell & Clark, 2018). Quantitative research enables the use of larger sample sizes and broader analytical perspectives due to its systematic, rigorous, and controlled approach to data collection (Dörnyei, 2007). In contrast, qualitative inquiry offers researchers valuable in-depth insights into the complexities of individual behavior, beliefs, and experiences (J. W. Creswell & Poth, 2018). EMI is a complex program that requires a thorough analysis to understand the overall situation. While measurable outcomes provide a surface view, considering contextual factors allows for a complete understanding of the scenario. A mixed-method design enables a comprehensive analysis of a phenomenon such as EMI, often necessitating the combination of numerical data and narrative accounts (J. W. Creswell & Clark, 2018). This design ensures that quantitative and qualitative data contribute uniquely to answering the research questions.

3.2 Sampling & Participants

Stratified random sampling was used to select participants for this study to ensure representation across different subgroups of students of EMI programs at the University of Chittagong. This technique involves dividing students into groups based on shared characteristics such as discipline, academic year, and prior education medium and then randomly selecting participants from each group. (Som, 1996). Chittagong University currently offers two mediums of instruction: Bangla and English. This research purposively focused on students and teachers from EMI programs. Stratified random sampling is effective in this scenario as it “ensures the inclusion of relevant subgroups and enhances the precision of statistical inferences” (John W. Creswell, 2014).

A total of 189 students from various disciplines with EMI backgrounds participated in this research. After cleaning the data, 180 participants were selected, representing multiple academic years. The demographics of the participants are as follows: academic years: Masters (n=61), 4th Year (n=27), 3rd Year (n=30), 2nd Year (n=42), and 1st Year (n=20) across various disciplines: Arts (n=115), Business (n=35), and Science (n=30). Gender: Male (n=92), Female (n=88). The students' names were anonymized by randomly assigning them a code 'STD,' ranging from 'STD01' to 'STD180'. I have also taken data from eight EMI teachers. The teachers' names were anonymized by randomly assigning them the code 'T' with a number, for example, 'T01'. We have also selected these teachers' classrooms to conduct class observations.

Although the study initially used purposive sampling to concentrate on EMI participants, Stratified random sampling made the results more reliable by reducing sample bias and making sure that important subgroups were represented (Kothari, 2004).

Figure 3.1: Demographic information of the students

Figure 3.2: Demographic information of the teachers

3.3 Data Collection

3.3.1 Instrument

The instruments were carefully selected to align with the objectives and effectively address the research questions: a structured questionnaire and classroom observation. These tools were designed to capture both quantitative metrics and qualitative insights.

3.3.2 Questionnaires

Questionnaires are “a widely used method for collecting data from a large number of respondents in a relatively short period of time” (Bryman, 2012). Dörnyei (2007) discusses questionnaires in his book *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*, highlighting their “extremely versatile and uniquely capable” nature for collecting data from a large number of participants efficiently and systematically. In this study, the questionnaires were an essential instrument for gathering insights into the experiences, perceptions, and challenges faced by students and teachers at the University of Chittagong regarding English Medium Instruction (EMI). Two separate questionnaires were developed for teachers and students, which combined closed-ended and open-ended questions to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. Close-ended questions primarily include Likert scales, which are effective for capturing attitudes, challenges, and perceptions with measurable precision (Likert, 1932). Open-ended questions are useful to gain a deeper understanding of respondents’ experiences and challenges. They enable responders to share their perspectives in their own words, providing context and depth to the research findings (John W. Creswell, 2014). Questionnaires designed for teachers mostly consist of open-ended questions, allowing them to elaborate on their practices and challenges.

A set of 28 questions was designed for students, consisting of both quantitative and qualitative questions. The questionnaire was structured into five sections to collect the necessary data in alignment with our objectives and research questions. The initial section of the questionnaire sought information regarding the participants’ demographics and background. These data are important for analyzing patterns and correlations within the dataset. (Bryman, 2012). The second section gathered data regarding participant’s experience with EMI. These data are important as they examine the direct influence of EMI on academic performance and classroom performance. Likert-scale items measure subjective experiences while ensuring analytical accuracy (Cohen et al., 2007). Open-ended questions gather detailed insights from students. In the fourth section, the questionnaire includes targeted questions to identify the specific challenges students encounter and their perceptions of EMI. Section five includes questions designed to gather students’ open-ended opinions and experiences of EMI, adding qualitative depth to the analysis.

Table 3.1: Questionnaire items (Students)

Section	Questions	Question Type
1. Demographics and Background	Discipline Gender Type of area where you completed your SSC Type of area where you completed your HSC	Close-ended Close-ended Close-ended Close-ended
2. Experience with English-Medium Instruction (EMI)	What was your first-year GPA? What is the last GPA result you've gained? How do your teachers conduct your class? How would you like your class to be conducted? My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction? Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English? How is EMI (English Medium Instruction) influencing your overall performance in exams? Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skills?	Close-ended Close-ended Open-ended Open-ended Likert-scale Likert-scale Open-ended Likert-scale Likert-scale
3. Exam Preparation and Strategies	Which class activity do you fear the most? How do you prepare yourself for exams? Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams? I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exams. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas.	Open-ended Open-ended Close-ended Likert-scale Likert-scale

	I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result.	Likert-scale
4. Language Skills and Confidence	During class, do you feel anxious when asked to express your ideas or if you need to ask questions in English?	Likert-scale
	Are you confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills?	Likert-scale
	I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program.	Likert-scale
	I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English.	Likert-scale
	I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty.	Likert-scale
	I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports.	Likert-scale
	I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant.	Likert-scale
5. Other Opinions and Experiences	Your opinion on English-Medium Instruction (EMI).	Open-ended
	Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?	Open-ended

13 questions were designed for the teachers' questionnaire, mostly featuring open-ended questions. These questions were divided into five sections, each tailored to a specific theme. The first section identifies teachers' demographics and backgrounds, which helps to situate their experiences within their educational and professional contexts. These information are important to understand their perspective. The second section collects their classroom practices and the challenges encountered in the EMI classroom. This information is crucial for identifying

areas that require institutional support and policy recommendations. The third section sought to gather information regarding their pedagogical training and their expectations for effectively conducting an EMI class. This information highlights the gaps in teacher training and the shortage of resources. Fourth section focus on teachers’ teaching strategies and feedback mechanisms that enhance classroom dynamics. In the fifth section, open-ended questions were designed to gather teachers’ opinions on why some teachers are not delivering their full classes in English, as well as their suggestions for new teachers transitioning to English medium instruction from a Bangla medium background.

Table 3.2: Questionnaire items (Teachers)

Section	Questions	Question Type
1. Demographics and Background	Years teaching in English-medium instruction	Close-ended
	What was the medium of instruction in your undergraduate studies?	Close-ended
	Self-rated English proficiency	Likert-scale
2. Teaching Practices and Challenges	What language do you use for delivering class lectures?	Open-ended
	Comfort level delivering lectures completely in English	Likert-scale
	What percentage of your students understand your lectures delivered in English?	Likert-scale
	What challenges do you face delivering lectures in English?	Open-ended
3. Training and Support	Have you received any training/support/education for English-medium instruction?	Close-ended
	What will help you teach more effectively in English?	Open-ended
4. Encouraging Engagement and Feedback	How do you encourage student participation and engagement in English-medium classes?	Open-ended

	Do you receive feedback from students regarding their experience with English-medium instruction? If so, summarize common concerns or suggestions.	Open-ended
5. Suggestions for Transition	Why do you think teachers do not deliver their full class in English? What suggestions do you have for teachers transitioning to English-medium instruction?	Open-ended Open-ended

3.3.3 Classroom Observation

Classroom observation was conducted as a complementary data collection method for this study. Observations are a great way to record behaviors, strategies, and interactions as they happen naturally. They can reveal insights that might not occur through self-reported data from questionnaires or interviews (Cohen et al., 2007). In this study classroom observation helps us to verify and contextualize findings from questionnaires. This study's classroom observation centered on four key elements:

1. Language of instruction,
2. Teaching methods,
3. Student engagement, and
4. Classroom environment.

During the classroom observation, the use of English in lectures, discussions, interactions, and presentations was recorded, along with instances of code-switching and the use of Bangla by both students and teachers. Observations focus on teachers' explanations of complex concepts, their engagement with students as well as students' participation and their interactions with both teachers and peers. Signs of students' understanding of complex subjects were observed, along with the rapport between the teacher and students and the overall classroom atmosphere.

3.3.4 Procedures

The data collection was conducted in three phases. The questionnaire set that was designed for students was shared via Google Forms. Participants received an overview of the study, and a consent option was included, stating, “By clicking “Continue” or submitting your responses, you confirm that you understand what this research is about, voluntarily agree to participate, and consent to use the data you provide for the stated research purposes.” This guaranteed that participation was voluntary and that participants understood the purpose and use of their responses. The data were then exported to Google Sheets. Participants’ anonymity was maintained by assigning them random sample numbers through a spreadsheet formula. Questionnaires designed for teachers were distributed offline, and their handwritten responses were entered into an Excel sheet for effective data analysis. Classroom observations were conducted over a period of 5 days in which eight classes were observed each lasting about 45 minutes. During each session, field notes were taken with a focus on the predefined observation area. The observations took place without disrupting the classroom environment, with the researcher positioned at the back of the classroom.

3.4 Data Analysis Technique

The collected data for this study was analyzed using quantitative and qualitative methods, depending on the data type. Quantitative data analysis has been conducted using Microsoft Excel, IBM SPSS Statistics (version 25), and Python (version 3.12.0). The questionnaire includes several Likert scales that evaluate participants’ language proficiency, academic challenges, and their experiences and perceptions of the EMI program. We measured the reliability of these questions using Cronbach’s alpha (α) coefficient by using Python in the Jupyter Notebook (see Appendix for the code). The Cronbach’s alpha (α) value for the questions is 0.85, which, according to Cohen et al. (2007), suggests a strong level of reliability.

Section	Cronbach's Alpha
Experience with EMI	0.857
Language Skills and Confidence	0.848
Combined (all Likert-scale items)	0.847

Table 3.3: Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability test

Microsoft Excel was used for descriptive statistical analysis. We used SPSS to identify correlations and significant differences, such as the differences in students' EMI experiences. For example, We correlated participants' English proficiency with the location of their previous studies. Both Excel and Python were used for data visualization.

Thematic analysis was conducted on qualitative data using both manual methods and NVivo (version 15) to identify key challenges and perceptions. Responses were organized according to themes, such as teaching methods, teachers' backgrounds, medium of instruction, and student engagement. Thematic analysis of class observations is conducted to improve data validity and incorporate a third perspective.

3.5 Ethical Procedures

Rigorous ethical guidelines were followed throughout all stages of the study. Participants were well-informed about the study's purpose, benefits, and potential risks. The survey forms included a section for consent, indicating that participants were voluntarily giving their consent. Their data were anonymized. Following the class observation, teachers and students were notified and asked for their consent to use the collected data to minimize observational bias. This study includes only data for which consent was obtained, and the information regarding teachers has been kept confidential. The survey data is stored in a password-protected Google Drive account, accessible only to the researcher.

Chapter 4

Findings and Data Analysis

This chapter presents the findings of the statistical and qualitative analyses of the data collected for this study, which aim to answer our research questions. The data analysis is performed in two sections: the first from the students' survey and the second from the teachers' questionnaire. The classroom observation report will work as supplementary material for validating and contextualizing the findings for both the students' survey and the teachers' questionnaire.

4.1 Analysis of Students' Survey Data

4.1.1 Participants' Demographics

The research methodology already provides a general overview of the participant's demographic. We have categorized students' demographics based on their current discipline, academic year, and gender to have an inclusive and fair result. Within the discipline category, the percentages of arts, business, and science are as follows - 63%, 19%, and 18%. Participation from students across all academic years, from first-year to master's, was ensured. Gender is also considered, so male and female participation was ensured, comprising 51% and 49%. To understand how students view English and the influence of their educational background, we also gathered their geographic information data, that is, the type of area where they completed their SSC and HSC.

Figure 4.1: Geographic distribution of students

Here, we can see that 5% of SSC students and 2% of HSC students come from remote areas comprising hill tracts, islands, etc. At the SSC level, 28% and 26% of HSC students come from suburban areas. At the SSC level, 43% and 63% of HSC students come from urban areas. At the SSC level 5% and at the HSC level 2%, students come from remote areas comprising hill tracts, islands, etc. This data tells us that a significant number of students move to urban areas after completing their SSC. The reason for this can be interlinked with the facilities that the urban center provides, which include quality education, academic opportunities, and specialized coaching. The background of students' prior education impacts their tertiary education. The percentage of students coming from non-English backgrounds is 92%, whereas just 8% of students come from English backgrounds at The University of Chittagong.

Figure 4.2: Students' prior medium of instructions

This finding suggests that most EMI students at the University of Chittagong come from non-English backgrounds.

4.1.2 Students' Academic Language Proficiency

Statistical analysis was conducted using the Likert scale data to measure students' English language proficiency. Students were asked to self-assess their skills, and four English skill sets were measured: their listening skills, reading skills, writing skills, and speaking skills. They have responded on a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree).

	Listening Skill	Reading Skill	Writing Skill	Speaking Skill
Average (Mean)	3.44	3.22	3.00	2.20
Standard Deviation	0.77	0.85	0.85	1.08
Minimum Score	1	1	1	1
Maximum Score	4	4	4	4

Table 4.1: Self-rated language proficiency

The questionnaire was set as follows to find out their listening skills: "I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English." Here, we can see in the table 4.1 that the mean score is 3.44, which indicates that students generally feel confident in understanding class lectures delivered in English. The 0.77 standard deviation suggests that most students listening skills in English are close to the average score. The questionnaire "I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty" measured students' reading skills. In this questionnaire, they self-rated their reading skills with a median score of 3.22, which suggests that the student's reading comprehension of academic subjects is above average. However, the standard deviation of 0.85 indicates that there is slightly more variability in reading comprehension than in reading comprehension. "I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports" was the questionnaire used to measure students' writing skills. The mean score of 3.00 indicates a moderate level of confidence in students' writing skills, while the standard deviation suggests slight variability in the skills among different students. To measure students' speaking skills, the questionnaire stated, "I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly

hesitant.” The average measurement of 2.20 indicates the lowest mean among the four skills, which suggests that among all the four English language skills, students face the most challenges in English during discussions or presentations. A standard deviation of 1.08 implies that some students may feel very confident in English speaking while others feel much less confident. The findings suggest that students demonstrate a solid grasp of listening and reading skills, but they struggle with speaking and writing, particularly speaking. These findings of the students’ lack of English speaking skills were compared with students’ classroom anxiety levels. Students’ level of anxiety was assessed through the statement, “During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.” A Spearman’s rank correlation was performed which is shown in the table 4.2.

Variable	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
Speaking Skill	1.000	.
Classroom Anxiety	-0.743**	0.000

Table 4.2: Spearman’s Correlation Table

Note: **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

After performing the test, we can see that there is a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.743$) between students’ speaking skills and anxiety levels. This suggests that students’ anxiety level is related to their speaking skills, and as students’ English speaking skills improve, students’ anxiety levels will also decrease significantly. The significant p-value ($p < 0.01$) confirms this correlation is statistically significant.

These findings suggest that the University of Chittagong’s EMI program may need to include targeted language support to improve students’ English-speaking skills.

4.1.3 Current EMI Situation

To check the current EMI situation at The University of Chittagong regarding language use in the classroom, how teachers teach, how engaged students are in class, and how students think their lessons should be taken is analyzed.

4.1.3.1 Language Use in the Classroom

Students were asked, “How do your teachers conduct your class?” to evaluate the language their teachers use in the classroom. This inquiry aimed to determine whether teachers use a single language, implement a language immersion method, or engage in code-mixing during instruction.

Figure 4.3: Classroom language usage

Analyzing the data, we can see in figure 4.3 that 89.42% of the students reported that teachers deliver their lectures using code-mixing, whereas about 52% of students reported that their teachers conduct their classes using mostly Bangla with a little English, and other 37% of students reported that teachers take their entire class mainly using English with a little Bangla. 7.94% of the students reported that teachers take their entire classes in Bangla, and only 2.65% reported that teachers take classes in English. Upon conducting class observations, our observations confirmed this finding. We found that in EMI classes at the University of Chittagong, most teachers primarily use Bangla for their lectures and use English mainly when they read books. In our observation of eight classes, only two teachers were seen mostly taking their entire class in Bangla. However, both datasets reveal that code-mixing teaching is mainly used, and Bangla is teachers’ preferred language of instruction.

We observed teachers’ teaching approaches while observing EMI classroom language practice. Our observation found that the majority of teachers who use mostly English with Bangla to explain subject content used traditional reading and translation methods in the EMI classroom, which focuses on reading from textbooks and then translating and explaining the content in

Bangla. Classes seemed less engaging, as the teachers mostly relied on prescribed books or pre-prepared slides. Due to less interaction, students generally didn't have any scope to develop their speaking skills, hindering EMI's objectives.

4.1.3.2 Challenges in Conducting Lectures in English: Students' Perspectives

Opinions were asked of the students to find out why their teachers did not take their entire English class.

Figure 4.4: Challenges in conducting lectures in English: Students' perspectives

The data for this question was then coded to analyze the qualitative response, and five key themes were created from their response. The first theme, **Student Comprehension and Comfort**, as shown in figure 4.4, highlights that close to 30% of the students think that teachers do not conduct their entire classes in English due to the majority of the students coming from non-English medium backgrounds, so for students' comprehension and comfort. For instance, participants (STD8) and (STD91) mentioned:

“As most of the students are not from English medium & have a little proficiency in English, it becomes difficult to understand the class lectures when teachers conduct their whole lessons in English. I think that's the reason”.

“Though teachers know English, they feel comfortable teaching in Bangla because most of the students admitted to this university are from Bangla medium backgrounds.”

The second theme, as shown in the figure 4.4 is **Teacher fluency and comfort**. This theme includes students' perception that teachers' own English proficiency and comfort are responsible for their language choice during lectures. Many students expressed concern that some teachers may lack the necessary English proficiency or confidence to take a full lecture in English. For example STD40 and STD90 commented:

“Teachers lack the skill that is needed to conduct a full class in English, as most of them come from Bangla medium instruction.”

“They're also not capable of doing so. Except two-three teachers, other teachers' English skill is average.”

Such responses suggest that teachers' language choice may not just influenced by students' comfort level and comprehension but also by the teacher's ability and comfort in taking an entire class in English.

The third theme, **Easier Understanding in Bangla**, highlights students' perception that teachers do not use English for their entire classes due to their belief that students' native language, Bangla, will be more effective for explaining complex topics. For example, STD35 and STD52 expressed:

“I guess it's convenient to express complex ideas in a simpler way when conveyed in Bangla since it's their first/mother language.”

“May be they can explain the topic in Bangla better than English or they think you can understand it better in Bangla.”

Exam-oriented curriculum and **mixed method for effectiveness** are our last two themes for this analysis. Some students feel that the university curriculum is exam-oriented, so teachers focus only on students' GPAs instead of practicing the English language in the classroom. STD100 commented:

“teachers think students' academic results are enough for their success, so they do not give any importance in taking classes in English.”

Other students think that teachers do not conduct entire classes in English because they feel code-mixing is effective for students of different backgrounds as it can gradually develop their English proficiency. For example, STD105 stated:

“English is our 2nd language so mixing English with Bangla can help us understand context better I think that’s why teachers do not take full classes in English.”

In analyzing the data related to the current EMI scenario at the University of Chittagong, it is also important to analyze students’ preferences regarding the language used in their EMI classrooms. The following section shows the data collected to understand these preferences.

4.1.3.3 Students’ Classroom Language Preference

A statistical analysis is performed to determine the language preferences of students regarding the language they wish their teachers to use in the classroom. The analyzed data is visualized in the figure 4.5

Figure 4.5: Students’ classroom language preference

The visualized data shows that 60.8% of the students want their teachers to take classes mainly using English with a minimum of Bangla for complex-topic understanding. 26.5% of students expressed their expectation that they want their teacher to take classes entirely in English. 11.6% of the students want their teachers to take classes using mainly Bangla and little English, and just 1.1% of students expressed that they wish teachers to take classes entirely in Bangla. This result highlights that most students are positive about teachers taking their entire class in English with a little code-mixing support for complex subject matter understanding. When students were asked if they believed that their English skills and understanding of subject

matter would be much better if the teachers took their full classes in English, the following result was found:

Category	Percentage
Strongly Agree(4)	50.79
Agree(3)	29.10
Disagree(2)	16.40
Strongly Disagree(1)	3.70

Statistic	Value
Mean	3.26984127
Standard Deviation	0.8667562887
Min	1
Max	4

Table 4.3: Distribution of responses for full lessons in English

From the table 4.3, we can see that around 80% of students feel that their understanding of English would be much better if their teachers took their full classes in English, whereas 50.79% of students strongly agree with the assertion, “My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English” and 29.10% students expressed that they agree with the statement. The mean value of 3.269 and a standard deviation of 0.866 indicate that a majority of students feel the necessity of having an English-immersed classroom within their EMI program.

4.1.4 Institutional Support: Preparatory Language Course

Researchers have advocated for preparatory English language courses for students with low English proficiency in EMI settings. Although, at present, no dedicated language courses are implemented in the EMI curriculum for students, let alone specific preparatory courses designed for specific language skills, the university has included a GED functional English course in the curriculum to tackle students’ English requirements. However, there is a lot of controversy regarding its effectiveness. A Likert scale was employed to determine students’ perception of

this course and whether they found it sufficient to meet their English needs. The result of the finding is shown in the table 4.4:

Statistic	Value
Average (Mean)	1.69
Standard Deviation	0.857
Minimum Score	1
Maximum Score	4

Table 4.4: GED course sufficiency survey

For the Likert scale, “I believe the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skills,” a four-point Likert scale was employed, with a minimum score of 1 and a maximum score of 4. If the students strongly believe the statement, they respond 4, and if they strongly disagree with it, they respond 1. After conducting statistical data analysis, we can see that the mean score is 1.69, which indicates that students strongly disagree with the statement and find EMI insufficient to meet their English skills requirement. The 0.857 standard deviation suggests that most students feel the same way about the GED Functional English course. STD110, when asked to give his opinion about EMI, expressed their disappointment about this course and expressed,

“no way the GED course is adequate to develop our English skills, Even HSC English has better syllabus than this.”

This statement highlights dissatisfaction among students about their GED functional English course and calls for a more robust preparatory language course.

4.1.5 Challenges in EMI: Students’ Perception

4.1.5.1 EMI Classroom Practice and Challenges

Students responded to a pre-tailored questionnaire and open-ended questions, expressing many of the challenges they face in EMI classrooms. Among those challenges, most of their answers to open-ended questions mentioned classroom anxiety and fear of being judged. In this section, we will first analyze the four-point Likert statement: “During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.”

We can see from the analysis that 70.90% of students reported that they strongly agreed with the statement. The mean value of 3.24 confirms that the majority of students experience anxiety

Figure 4.6: Students' Classroom anxiety

when they are asked to express their ideas or ask questions in English. This result gives us one possible reading, which is that students don't have an engaging and interactive environment where they can feel safe and don't have to fear making mistakes while practicing English. The practice of speaking English in EMI classrooms is crucial for its success. Practicing English in EMI classrooms is very crucial for its success, so we have asked EMI students why they feel this anxiety. Most of their responses point out one single thing: the fear of being judged. Students reported that their teachers tend to criticize them for their pronunciation, which they feel is an unnecessary aspect of the speaking skills. Participant STD81 gave the following response:

“The teachers should allow the students to make mistakes; they should not stop their students if they wrongly pronounce words. Teachers should remember that the purpose of a language should be to convey thoughts properly, not pronunciation like that of a native. Also, teachers should conduct their full class in English; if they lack the skills, they should practice it. It is also important to note that conducting a class only by reading books, online content, or slides is very boring; it takes away attention from the students. The main challenge that I faced was the lack of guidance. Classroom should be interactive and friendly; otherwise, it will discourage the students from participating”

Other participants also pointed out similar issues when they were asked to talk about their classroom activity experience. STD75 said,

“I felt confident after giving a presentation in 1st year. I received positive feedback from the teacher and was praised for my accent. It helped boost my confidence

for later presentations. While I am confident giving presentations as I can prepare beforehand, I do sometimes struggle with spontaneous speech in English. Some reasons include - nervousness, unfamiliarity with a subject being talked about, or just that I am introvert in nature. During a presentation in 4th year, I was interrupted twice by the teacher for mispronouncing. It was annoying and it made me feel nervous.”

Here, we can see that both participants shared how they feel demotivated and anxious. This can greatly hinder their language acquisition. According to the affective filter hypothesis proposed by S. Krashen (1982), students’ emotional condition greatly affects their second language learning. In this case, students’ anxiety, fear of making mistakes, or lack of confidence can raise a filter that hinders students’ speaking skills. If we apply Krashen’s affective filter hypothesis here, we can relate students’ English speaking challenges with high affective filters like teacher’s interruption, criticism, and judgments, which made it hard for the students to participate in the classroom in English.

We tried to verify this finding by asking students, “Which class activity do you fear most?” The University of Chittagong utilizes a class assessment system that comprises three activities: Assignment, Presentation, and Class Test (CT). Each course teacher is required to conduct the class assessment, which then turns into a score out of 25. After aggregating the assessments from all courses and calculating the percentage, this score of 25 is then added to the overall academic result. Although most students don’t like assessments yet, they are still an important part of the academic requirement. Our findings from the questionnaire help us determine which class task students fear most. The finding of the questionnaire is given below:

Figure 4.7: Classroom activity that students fear most

From the figure 4.7, we can see that 85.2% of students expressed anxiety about presentation. However, presenting is relatively easy compared to CT, as in CT, one must recall numerous details and then write them down, whereas, in a presentation, one uses slides to cover the entire content. This finding showcases the lack of confidence and fear of speaking in English among EMI students. This fear may come from limited vocabulary and critical feedback from teachers, as noted by STD65,

“During my presentation, when I can’t represent the topic beautifully for lack of sufficient English words, it feels demotivating and it further decreases my confidence when teacher criticises me harshly for my pronunciation.”

To help students overcome their speaking challenges and lower affective filters, S. Krashen (1982) suggests that institutions should build an environment where students can express themselves without the fear of making mistakes and being judged by others.

4.1.5.2 Challenges in Exams

Exams are generally the scale on which students’ development is judged. Most stakeholders only use this scale to check students’ overall academic performance. So, it is important to check whether students are facing challenges in taking exams, and if yes, how many challenges they are facing and what they are doing about them. In our pilot study, we created a hypothesis that in the initial year of the EMI program, students tend to face challenges in exams due to their prior Bangla medium background, which led to poor results. As we have chosen participants from every academic year, We have asked them about their first-year GPA to verify our hypothesis. The responses are grouped into five categories based on academic year. The analysis result is shown in the table 4.5.

Study Year	Mean	σ
1st year	2.988	0.155
2nd Year	2.973	0.145
3rd Year	3.008	0.331
4th Year	2.987	0.261
Masters	3.001	0.275
Avg. Total	2.991	

Table 4.5: Students’ first-year final exam results (GPA)

According to the analyses, we can see that students from all academic years have an average

GPA of 2.99 out of a GPA of 4.00. This result validates our hypothesis that most students get a poor GPA in their initial year of EMI program. When we asked them about it to understand what could be the reason behind it, STD29 responded that,

“I get really frustrated in the exam hall when I know the answer but I cannot write it properly because I think of the answer in Bangla but I’ve to write it in English.”

This response highlights the influence of students’ prior medium of education on their thinking ability as they need to think about the answer in Bangla first. Then, they have to translate the answers into English. Lack of vocabulary also becomes challenging for the students as institutions don’t have any robust preparatory language courses in the curriculum. To tackle this, students rely on rote memorization, as expressed by STD30,

“In the first year, I took the exam by memorizing the previous year’s question answers. But after that, I tried to understand each topic and write it in my own way.”

Rote memorization can be detrimental to students, as it limits their capacity for critical thinking and stifles creativity. Upon reviewing the past ten years of examination questions from various departments, we observed a notable pattern of repetition. It appears that approximately 80% of the questions tend to recur from previous years’ examinations. So, when students follow this pattern, most of the students tend to depend on the previous years’ exam questions. To verify this, we asked students how many of them followed previous years’ questions for exam preparation. The result is shown in the figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Count of Students’ Dependency on Previous Years’ Exam Questions

This figure shows that almost 97.8% of students follow previous years’ exam questions for their exam preparation, and among them, 19% totally depend on them, resulting in a lack of

understanding of the subject. This tendency negatively impacts students' learning attitudes and their writing skills, as they tend to write only what they have memorized.

Students also reported that they needed time to understand the questions because of their inexperience with English medium questions. STD37, when asked about their experience with exam questions in their first year, reported that-

“I had to read very carefully and take my time to interpret the meaning of the questions. It took a lot of time. But from second semester it gradually became easier. Now it does not influence my performance in exams as it did before.”

The statement of STD37 is true for most students; as we have observed over time, students' GPA increases gradually. We have asked the first-year GPAs of students and their subsequent GPAs to assess the extent of their improvement over the years. The analysis of the responses is given below.

Figure 4.9: Students' Academic Improvement Over Time

Figure 4.9 illustrates the student GPA trend over the year. The blue dotted line represents the first-year GPA of students, while the solid orange line denotes the last obtained GPA of those students. The blue lines indicate that students generally start with low GPAs in their first year, but a noticeable improvement arises in their second year. Although the GPA of the students slightly decreases in their third year due to the inclusion of an extra eight credits for the third and fourth years, students again show significant improvement in their GPAs in the fourth year—the positive trajectory peaks at the Master's level with an average GPA of almost 3.4. However, this is not the case for every student because the extra pressure of learning a new language and the pressure of higher education subjects can become a burden for some, which results in students'

failure in the exam and loss of an academic year. A participant from Master’s (STD133) reported the following statement-

“We study in arts discipline where subjects are easier than STEM subjects so students of arts faculty generally pass the exam just by reading two nights before the exam but when it comes to our subject its very hard to deal with new language and we need to give extra effort, when I was in my first year six of my friends failed in the exam and had to continue with other batch, later i heard that two of them was dropped out from university, another two also failed in the second year. So I think departments can provide extra classes for the students who are weak in English so that they can get a good result.”

We also wanted to know if the institutions’ efforts to provide a good learning environment and academic support are the only reason why students receive good grades or if there are other factors that contribute to students’ gradual success, such as rote memorization of previous years’ questions. This investigation was prompted by the observation that most teachers tend to compose traditional, bookish questions that they repeat every year. We have also wanted to find out whether students are using the internet, YouTube, etc., to gain a better understanding outside of the classroom. To get a better sense of these factors, we asked students some questions about how they prepare for the exam. The analysis of the collected data of the questions is given below-

	Mean	SD
I rely on memorizing questions and suggestions for exams	2.94	0.51
I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas	1.91	0.97
I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a descent result	2.57	0.89

*Note: ** Min = 1, Max =4 ***

Table 4.6: Students’ tactics for exam preparation

Table 4.6 shows that, on average, students rated 2.94 out of 4 on a Likert scale regarding their reliance on rote memorization of suggestions provided by teachers before their exams and the questions they derive from analyzing previous years’ exam questions. The average response of 1.91 out of 4 on a Likert scale suggests a lower inclination towards understanding the topic. So, we can see that students generally tend to memorize content to pass the exam or get good marks instead of understanding the subject matter. Which greatly hinders the purpose of education and

the repetition of questions plays a big role in creating such a mentality among students, as the average response of 2.57 for the statement “I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result” suggests that most students agree that studying past questions can lead to decent results.

Another aspect that affects students’ success is their high reliability on tools like the Web, YouTube, and AI for exam preparation, which is visualized in figure 4.10. Therefore, it is evident that the Internet, artificial intelligence, YouTube, and similar resources have a more significant impact on improving students’ academic outcomes than the institution itself. STD90 expressed that -

“Since our medium of instruction is English, we had to learn English from several sources such as using youtube, dictionaries and other apps. These activities somehow made us capable to write in exam but i think department or faculties have no contribution in this.”

Figure 4.10: Students’ Exam Preparation Method

4.1.6 Students’ Perceptions About EMI

Students’ perceptions regarding English-medium instructions vary from individual to individual. Students coming from English curricula find EMI easier than those with a Bangla curriculum background. STD35 expressed that-

“Since I’ve studied in English version, I would say it has been easier for me compared to someone who transitioned from Bangla medium to English medium.”

Table 4.7 highlights the findings of the questionnaires that seek to find students' overall experience with EMI, its influence on their academic performance, improvements in their English communication skills, and their confidence in seeking job opportunities following the completion of the program. In order to arrive to this conclusion, we analyzed a few statements from the Likert scale, including "My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university," "Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction," "I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills," "I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program. " Students were instructed to evaluate these statements by assigning points from 1 to 4, with 1-2 indicating a negative response and 3-4 indicating a positive response.

Metric	Mean	SD
Overall Experience with EMI	3.36	0.76
Impact on Academic Performance	3.21	1
Improvement in Communication Skills	3.1	0.97
Confidence in Seeking Job Opportunities	2.69	1.23

Table 4.7: Students' Perceptions About EMI

Our data analysis shows that most students have a positive experience with EMI, with a mean score of 3.36 and a comparatively low standard deviation of 0.76. Students have given us information about the challenges that they face in EMI classrooms, but there are some instances where teachers' positive feedback can hugely improve students' overall experience in EMI, as suggested by STD75-

"I felt confident communicating in English in class during a presentation. My lecturer played an important role in that. They encouraged me to speak without stopping or correcting me midway. At first I was anxious about the shift to English Medium from Bangla medium. Later, I adapted by continuously practicing speaking in English in both inside and outside of class. I used to practice talking in front of mirror. Also English newspaper, books & movies helped me a lot. I felt discouraged after doing a poor result in one of the classes but later I talked with my teacher and followed his guidelines. I've always been scared of failure but my teacher was the first one who said it's okay to make mistakes. Students have to keep in mind one thing that

their accent doesn't really matter. They need to focus on fluency rather than accuracy. Everything takes time, it's better to keep track of their improvement. Keeping a journal is the best."

The mean score of 3.21 for the impact of EMI on students' academic performance indicates a positive perception of EMI among students. Still, the standard deviation of 1 indicates some noticeable variability in individual experiences. This implies that while some students experience a positive impact on their learning experience, others may face challenges due to their varying proficiency levels. Students also responded positively about their improvement in different English skill sets, with a mean score of 3.31. A participant (STD41) expressed that-

"EMI has significantly impacted my performance in exams as it has improved my language proficiency and comprehension skills. It has provided me with a strong foundation in English language skills, which has directly influenced my overall performance in exams. Now I feel more confident in expressing my ideas and thoughts during exams, leading to better results."

However, regarding confidence in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills, the mean score drops to 2.69, with a standard deviation of 1.23. This result indicates a moderate level of confidence among students when it comes to seeking job opportunities. For example, STD62 expressed that-

"I used to hesitate to continue a conversation in English as I thought I had less fluency in it. But with time the overall conditioning of EMI somehow helped me to polish my ability. Though I haven't yet completely become proficient in it but the hesitancy and reluctance has dwindled to an extent."

However, the result also highlights a significant level of variability among students, indicating that some are highly confident in seeking job opportunities that require a strong English background, while others are less confident in this regard.

4.2 Analysis of Teachers' Questionnaire Data

4.2.1 Teachers' Demographics and Classroom Practices

We have selected eight teachers for this study. The teachers we chose had varying amounts of EMI experience, ranging from 2.5 to 20 years. We wanted to know their prior medium of instruction and their choice of classroom language. The findings are shown in figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11: Teachers' Prior MOI and Classroom Language Preference

Out of eight teachers, five have a Bangla-medium background, and only three have an English-medium background. Academic background plays a significant role in their comfort with EMI; henceforth, we can see that most teachers take classes using code-mixing and mostly use Bangla while code-mixing. None of the teachers conduct their classes entirely in English. When they were asked why teachers do not take their entire classes in English, teachers gave varying answers; some stated that they do not conduct entire classes in English to ensure better comprehension for students. However, the majority explained that their limited fluency in English, stemming from factors such as their background, insufficient practice, and a lack of comfort, is the primary reason for this choice. Teachers (T03) and (T04) stated that ,

“Most of the teachers’ mother tongue is Bangla. Thus, they lack confidence and comfort in delivering lectures in English. They don’t receive proper training in conducting English-medium classes. Our education system focuses on reading and writing skills over speaking and conversational skills.”

“ Teachers are not fluent in English themselves; to balance the different types of students coming from different backgrounds with language variations.”

A teacher (T02)) with 20 years of experience teaching EMI mentioned that apart from students' lack of comprehension skills and teachers' incapacity to conduct an entire class in English, teachers do not conduct entire classes in English due to their intention to reduce the mental effort (cognitive load) required to understand and process information in a second language. They stated that,

“While one very obvious reason for not delivering a full class in English is the student's lack of English comprehension skill, there are other issues like teacher's incapability to conduct a full session in English, and also, the teacher's propensity inclination to reduce the cognitive load of processing L2 when they are delivering the lecture or giving instructions on the class.”

Teacher (T03) also identified classroom size, students' fluency level, and their attitudes towards the English language as challenges encountered while delivering lectures in English, as they stated that-

“The background and levels of the students, different types of attitudes, aptitudes, and approaches of the students, and classroom size can be identified as challenges while delivering lectures in English .”

Sometimes, students also request the teacher to shift from English to Bangla to explain complex technical terms, that are very difficult for the students to grasp. The teacher (T02) expressed that-

“Because some students fail to comprehend a good portion of the lecture in English due to their poor comprehension skill, sometimes there are requests to explain the concepts in Bangla (L1). Sometimes the technical terms and language of the textbooks are very difficult for them and they are unable to make a relation between the lectures and the text. A simplified handout could be helpful for the students. ”

This statement necessitates the inclusion of handouts for helping students deal with complex subject matter instead of language shifting.

4.2.1.1 Pedagogical Training and Institutional Support

When asked if they had received any training on taking EMI classes, only one teacher out of eight said they had. Given that most teachers come from a Bangla medium background, it is important

Figure 4.12: Pedagogical Constraints

that they receive pedagogical training prior to entering the EMI program, a requirement that is mainly absent in the institution. Teacher (T04) advocated for the inclusion of proper teacher training when they were asked what would help them teach more effectively in English, as they mentioned the following requirements -

“Proper training and regular practice, adequate options to promote speaking skill,s and using technology (e.g., ChatGPT, YouTube) can help teachers teach more effectively.”

Teachers (T01), (T02), and (T08) suggested that the incorporation of technological facilities, such as visual aids and multimedia, might improve the effectiveness of English instruction.

4.2.2 Suggestions for Teachers Transitioning to EMI

At the end of our data collection from teachers, we asked them what suggestions they could provide for teachers transitioning to EMI so that they can teach efficiently. Based on their practical teaching experience of EMI, it was very important to know their perceptions and suggestions.

Teacher (T02) suggests that at the beginning of the program, the institute should assess students’ English language comprehension skills so that the institute can tailor its teaching strategy based on students’ needs. They also emphasized on teachers’ classroom management skills to help students deal with new learning environment. They noted that,

“Teachers should try to hone their linguistic skills first, either through in person training or using online platforms. Besides, they would need to develop classroom management skill. It would be great if they can make a survey among the students at the beginning of the course to get an idea of the students’ English language comprehension level which would help them to decide what strategies they should apply in the class to make the lectures comprehensible for the students.”

Some of the teachers emphasize getting pedagogical training on how to conduct lectures in an EMI setting. One teacher (T03) suggested that teachers should use the language immersion technique even if both the students and teachers feel uncomfortable, and over time, they might get comfortable with it. They stated that -

“They should teach in English relinquishing the native language for the time being. They should teach in English keeping in mind the academic purposes and the educational policies and values and to bring a social change.”

These insights from teachers suggest the need for teachers to improve their linguistic and classroom management skills, adjust their teaching strategies to meet students’ needs, and adopt a gradual language immersion approach, all of which can support a more effective and inclusive EMI learning environment.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

This chapter summarizes and discusses the key findings of the study; it then concludes the findings by presenting answers to the research questions, policy recommendations, and limitations of the study, and offers suggestions for future research directions.

5.1 Discussion

5.1.1 Student's Prior Background and its Impact on EMI Experience

The results obtained from descriptive statistic analysis reflect an inclusive demographic of the students. The results highlight that most of the students (92%) in the EMI program of The University of Chittagong come from a non-English-medium background. A good portion of these students come from remote and rural areas of Bangladesh, where the quality of education is below average. Most of the schools and colleges with Bangla-medium instruction, especially in nonurban areas, do not have facilities that provide comprehensive language teaching for English subjects, which can help students build a good foundation in English. Thus, the students lack comprehensive input for language acquisition. According to the Input Hypothesis by S. D. Krashen (1985), due to a lack of such input, students from such backgrounds often find themselves in a disadvantaged situation with a poor foundation in English. This creates inequality among students in their EMI classroom, which confirms the findings by Ernesto Macaro (2018) on inequalities in multilingual EMI classrooms.

5.1.2 Students' Self-Assessed Language Proficiency

To use language professionally and academically, an individual needs to have four language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These skills allow an individual to fully comprehend and express themselves. The students' self-assessment revealed an inconsistency in proficiency in the four language skills. The results indicate that students generally demonstrate strong performance in listening and reading. A mean score of 3.44 for listening and 3.22 for reading indicates that most students have a good comprehension level. So, if their class is taken in English, they will have good proficiency in understanding their academic texts. A mean score of 3.00 indicates that students have moderate proficiency in their writing, which means students have the ability to express their ideas in text. However, opinions collected from the students tell us that apart from English as a subject, they are not used to giving answers in the English exams before the EMI program; thus, they generally face challenges in their initial year of the EMI program.

Students' speaking skills were identified as the weakest skills, with a mean score of 2.20. This indicated that students felt less confident in expressing their ideas and thoughts. The significant negative correlations between students' speaking skills and classroom anxiety indicate that students tend to be afraid of making mistakes, which hinders their speaking skills in the classroom. This can be associated with the monitor hypothesis by S. Krashen (1988), which suggests that students often become self-aware while speaking a second language (L2) due to their emphasis on grammatical structure. Thus, they fear of making mistakes. This fear affects their spontaneous speaking in the classroom. H. Rahman & Kaur (2018) identified this psychological barrier as a significant obstacle to language development and classroom engagement. So, we wanted to check if there are more reasons behind students' weakest skills among all language skills.

5.1.2.1 Psychological Barriers to Classroom Engagement

About 70.9% of students said they feel anxious when expressing their thoughts and ideas in English. Students also expressed their anxiety about giving presentations that require speaking in front of others. This anxiety comes from the fear of being judged by others and teachers' criticism of students' pronunciation and grammar accuracy. This creates feelings of anxiety

and a lack of motivation, which acts like a “filter” that makes it hard for students to speak spontaneously. The affective filter hypothesis by S. Krashen (1982) suggests that when a student’s affective filter is high, it can hinder a student’s language acquisition process. To help reduce anxiety when speaking, EMI teachers should encourage students to minimize focusing on grammar use. They should also let students speak without interruptions, even if mistakes happen. Institutions should create an environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves without worrying about making mistakes or being judged.

5.1.3 Teachers’ Classroom Practices

Teachers heavily rely on code-switching while conducting the classroom. Most students reported that 52.4% of the teachers generally use Bangla with a little English while conducting the class, and 37% conduct their class mainly using English and a little Bangla to explain the complex subject matter. The reason many teachers tend to use mostly Bangla could be linked to their backgrounds, as a significant number of them come from a Bangla Medium background. Students and teachers both agree that two main reasons behind teachers not taking entire classes in English are due to teachers’ limited fluency in English and some students’ lack of comprehension level due to their unequal starting points. When students were asked about their classroom language preference, 68% of the students expected their teachers to take their entire classes using English with a little Bangla to explain complex subject matters. 26.5% of the students expressed that the institute should facilitate a fully English immersion method for teaching. 79.89% of the students are positive that their English skills and understanding of Subject matter would be better if teachers took their entire classes in English.

Classroom observation also highlights less engaging classrooms due to most teachers using traditional text-centered teaching, where teachers read from a book or pre-prepared slides or ask students to read. Then, they translate and explain the content in Bangla. Interactions between teachers and students are infrequent. Because there was less interaction, students usually generally don’t have much chance to improve their speaking skills, which made it hard to achieve the goal of EMI, which is to improve students’ English skills along with subject matters.

5.1.4 Insufficient Institutional Support

5.1.4.1 Lack of Preparatory English Language Course

To help students adapt to a new language as a medium of instruction, many researchers of EMI have advocated for preparatory language courses to improve students' language skills. The University of Chittagong includes a (GED) functional language course for students, but most of the students feel that it is totally insufficient to meet their needs. Apart from that, currently, there aren't any dedicated language courses included to aid students' specific language skills.

5.1.4.2 Insufficient Training for Teachers

Most teachers from EMI programs at The University of Chittagong reported not receiving any pedagogical training before starting teaching at the university. The findings of our study reveal that most teachers in EMI programs at the University of Chittagong completed their undergraduate studies in Bangla-medium instruction. This background makes it difficult for them to adapt to EMI classrooms without prior training. The institution also doesn't facilitate post-pedagogical support for teachers to aid them in teaching in EMI classrooms efficiently. This results in teachers highly resorting to code-switching, which compromises the objectives of EMI. Most teachers expressed the necessity of pedagogical training to overcome their teaching challenges.

5.1.5 Trends in Academic Performance and Coping Mechanism

Academic performance is crucial to judge students' success. Analysis of students' GPAs indicates that students generally struggle with lower GPAs in their initial year, with an average GPA of 2.99 out of 4.00. The reason behind this can be linked to their unfamiliarity with English questions, as they struggle with their writing skills. They have to tackle their low English language skills and understand complex subject matter. Students reported their struggle with their insufficient vocabulary; they needed to think in Bangla first, and then they had to translate them in the exam hall. This finding aligns with the findings of Graddol (2010), where they suggested that EMI can be a double burden as students must simultaneously struggle with language and academic challenges. However, from their second year, students' academic performance tends to develop as they get familiar with EMI and English writing. The coping mechanisms that

students develop to improve their GPAs include getting help from YouTube videos, ChatGPT, and other online materials. Many students said that instead of really understanding the subject and then writing in the exam, they rely on rote memorization. They reported that teachers often repeat questions instead of coming up with more creative ones. A lot of students think that reviewing last year's exams can help improve their GPA. Even though this coping mechanism helps students achieve good GPAs, it has long-term drawbacks. In a country like Bangladesh, where there is a shortage of jobs, most students focus on gaining good academic results instead of getting a good understanding of subjects. Institutions should focus on crafting more creative and unique exam questions so that students focus on understanding subjects more. As Ernesto Macaro (2017) cautions, such a strategy might compromise deeper learning and critical thinking. This strategy will ultimately prevent students from developing strong writing skills in English. To tackle this, the institute must design creative questions for students instead of repeating questions.

5.1.6 EMI Perception and Long-Term Perceived Benefits

Students have different experiences with English Medium Instruction (EMI). Some students, especially those who studied in English-medium schools, find it easier. For example, STD35 said, "Since I've studied in the English version, I would say it has been easier for me compared to someone who transitioned from Bangla medium." Many students shared that EMI helped them improve their English and academic performance. The average score for students' overall EMI experience was 3.36, and for communication skills, the mean was 3.1 out of 4, which suggests students' positive perception towards EMI and an improvement in their English communication skills after joining the program. For example, students mentioned challenges, especially at the beginning of the EMI program, such as anxiety about speaking English or fear of being judged by others, which, over the course of four years, some of them can overcome. STD75 noted, "At first I was anxious about the shift to English Medium from Bangla medium. Later, I adapted by continuously practicing speaking in English in both inside and outside of class." Teachers' encouragement also helped students feel more confident, as noted by STD75: "My lecturer encouraged me to speak without stopping or correcting me midway. That made a huge difference." However, when we tried to find out how EMI programs at The University of

Chittagong were doing in terms of preparing students for global competition and participation in international academic and professional networks, the analysis found that students felt less confident about their ability to pursue job opportunities that require English, as evidenced by their lower score of 2.69 out of 4. This result shows that institutions need to implement proper guidelines and modern facilities to help prepare students for the global market. The overall findings show that while a lot of students benefit from EMI, some still find it tough, especially those coming from Bangla-medium backgrounds.

5.2 Conclusion

This research emerged out of the necessity to address the academic impact and language challenges that students at the University of Chittagong face with the EMI program. This is especially relevant now, as EMI is gaining attention worldwide for its advantages in globalization and internationalization. We have tailored two research questions to find out how English Medium Instruction (EMI) impacts the academic performance and English proficiency of students who shift from other mediums of instruction to EMI and the challenges students and teachers face in an EMI setting. However, despite short-term challenges, Students appreciated EMI's long-term advantages, like better job prospects and global relevance.

In response to **RQ 1**, the study reveals that students generally experience a positive impact on their academic performance and English skills over time. Since most students come from non-English-medium backgrounds, they often face challenges in their first year as they lack prior exposure to the English language. These challenges and the double burden of mastering course content and language lead to lower GPAs in their first year. Nevertheless, the analysis observed that students gradually improved their academic results over time. On the other hand, most students improve their listening and reading skills significantly over the course of four years. They expressed that they feel more comfortable understanding lectures and academic texts in English. Students also reported a moderate improvement in their writing skills over time. However, analysis reveals that students' speaking skills are the weakest among all four language skills, as most students face challenges in spontaneous language use.

In response to **RQ 2**, our study identified a number of challenges that teachers and students face in an EMI setting. Students experience anxiety in classroom interaction when they are

asked to express their opinions in English or give a presentation due to fear of judgment, self-monitoring, and interruptions by teachers for their pronunciation. Students also expressed challenges in writing in English in exams as they struggle to find proper vocabulary and need extra time to think in Bangla and then translate their ideas into English. In a country like Bangladesh, where there is a shortage of jobs, most students focus on gaining good academic results instead of getting a good understanding of the subject matter. So, they heavily rely on memorizing previous years' questions with the help of ChatGPT and other online resources. Which hinders their critical thinking ability and deeper understanding of the subject matter. Teachers tend to repeat exams questions by following a pattern in designing exam questions, typically omitting questions from the most recent year while reusing questions from earlier years. To ensure EMI's success, this practice of teachers needs to be revised and restructured to prioritize critical thinking and conceptual understanding over rote learning for gaining good GPAs.

Teachers generally face challenges in taking their classes entirely in English as most of their MOI in bachelor's was Bangla. So, students and teachers both reported that due to teachers' insufficient language skills in taking their entire classes in English, most teachers tend to teach students mostly in Bangla, while reading the book in English. Some teachers also mentioned that they use mostly Bangla in the classroom because they think that students lack sufficient comprehension of the English language. Most of the students expect their teachers to take their classes using English with occasional Bangla if students ask them to. Due to teachers' lack of sufficient proficiency in English and their Bangla background, instead of extemporaneous lectures¹, they rely on traditional text-centered teaching, where teachers read from a book or pre-prepared slides or ask students to read. Then, they translate and explain the content in Bangla. This results in a lack of interaction in the EMI classroom, which makes it hard for students to engage and improve their English speaking skills.

The findings also highlight that even after completing, students of the EMI program may still lack full confidence in seeking global job opportunities that require strong English proficiency. So, it is important for EMI programs to make the curriculum more aligned with global workforce demands and ensure students are well-prepared to excel in international settings.

¹An extemporaneous lecture is a classroom teaching method in which the teacher gives information based on their own knowledge and written notes instead of reading straight from a script or textbook.

There are also limited institutional supports for both students and teachers as the institution doesn't have any preparatory language course in its syllabus to aid students in developing the specific skills that they lack. The institution also doesn't provide any pedagogical support that may help the teachers teach efficiently in EMI settings. Additionally, there isn't a specific policy at the institution for EMI, which causes the EMI program to not properly support students according to their needs, leading to frustration among students in their initial year. A holistic policy planning is a must for the university to overcome these challenges and align its EMI program with international standards.

5.2.1 Recommendations

In the light of the above findings in the study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the EMI program, with a focus on improving classroom teaching practices and supporting students' academic and language development.

1. The university should establish a centralized and comprehensive EMI policy framework that serves as a standard for its departments and institutions to follow as regulations. The policy framework should include guidelines for assessing students' current language skills, teachers' academic requirements, and compulsory teacher training to make the teachers fit for EMI teaching. The policy should also include a framework for a gradual language immersion system within the EMI program, along with regulated instruction on code-switching.
2. A well-tailored teacher training program with an English-speaking course must be included, as most teachers come from the Bangla medium of instruction. This will allow the teachers to be confident in taking classes in English. Regular professional development workshops on student-centered teaching approaches must be implemented so teachers can understand students' needs and the importance of positive feedback in building confidence among students.
3. The classroom environment needs to be student-friendly, interactive, and engaging. Teachers need to allow students to uninterruptedly make grammatical errors, mispronunciations, or regional pronunciations. Students' anxiety and fear of judgment should be mitigated by providing them with positive feedback, encouragements and counseling services.

4. To help students build confidence in using the English language and in seeking job opportunities that require English proficiency, workshops on public speaking, academic presentations, and writing can be arranged by the students' designated departments and institutions.
5. Departments and institutions that implement EMI programs at the university can establish language clubs, writing labs, and peer tutoring programs such as Student Teaching Student (STS). In language clubs, students can build confidence in English by watching English-language films and TV series, engaging in debates, and participating in peer-led speaking sessions. Teachers can guide students by providing clear improvement strategies, while students themselves can assist each other by reviewing written work and offering constructive feedback. Through STS, students with higher proficiency in English can tutor peers with lower proficiency.
6. The GED or General English Development course content needs to be enhanced to meet students' needs in higher education. Compulsory preparatory English language courses focusing on listening, speaking, reading, writing, and academic language skills need to be introduced.
7. Repeating exam questions promotes rote memorization and hinders critical thinking and writing skills. This practice needs to be reduced. Teachers should use various question types, including open-ended questions, case studies, and problem-solving scenarios, to enable students to apply their knowledge in multiple circumstances. This method enhances comprehension and critical thinking.
8. The university needs to create a clear language immersion policy to promote an English-speaking environment that helps students improve their fluency and confidence. In the early stages, controlled bilingual support should be allowed to ensure comprehension, with reliance on the native language progressively reduced over time; then, there can be a gradual shift to complete immersion in the following academic years.

5.2.2 Limitations

While conducting the study, it was not possible to ensure an equal number of participants from all departments of the university due to time constraints, as this is a Master's thesis. Self-reported data may introduce bias. To gain a true understanding of students' preparation for their long-term careers, a longitudinal study is necessary. Teaching styles among faculty members are not uniform, and data collected from teachers may not provide a comprehensive idea of their overall quality. Since this is a single university-centric study, it imposes certain limitations on the generalizability of the findings.

5.2.3 Future Research Directions

Future research should prioritize a more balanced participant representation across all university departments, ensuring more inclusive and representative findings. Longitudinal studies could reveal how students' career preparations evolve over time, providing insights into the long-term impact of their academic experiences. Researchers can identify factors that shape student outcomes and highlight effective methodologies by examining teaching practices across diverse departments. Including multiple universities in future studies would extend the applicability of results, offering a broader understanding of trends and influences. To reduce bias, alternative data collection methods could complement self-reported data.

5.2.4 Concluding remarks

This research was conducted to examine the impact and challenges of implementing English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) at the University of Chittagong. While EMI holds considerable promise for strengthening students' language skills, its effectiveness depends on contextual factors, including the academic backgrounds of both students and teachers, the degree of institutional support, and the underlying teaching practices.

The study analyzed student and teacher experiences, highlighting the importance of comprehensive preparatory language programs, proper teacher training, and robust institutional support. Based on these findings, it recommends a centralized EMI policy framework, a phased approach to language immersion, and targeted measures to help students overcome both linguistic and psychological challenges. The study also calls for more holistic research to determine EMI

graduates' long-term career outcomes.

Though this research represents just a small contribution to the vast research on EMI in higher education, I hope its findings encourage universities to foster environments where students can develop not only their academic results but also a deeper understanding of their subject matter and their communication skills, which are essential for the future academic pursuits or the global job market.

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Chapter A

Appendix

A.1 Supplementary Materials

A.1.1 Python Code for Cronbach's Alpha Calculation

The following Python script was used to calculate Cronbach's Alpha for analyzing the reliability of the questionnaire responses.

```
1 import pandas as pd
2 import numpy as np
3
4 # Function to calculate Cronbach's Alpha
5 def calculate_cronbach_alpha(df):
6     item_corr_matrix = df.corr()
7     n_items = len(df.columns)
8     mean_inter_item_corr = item_corr_matrix.mean().mean()
9     alpha = (n_items * mean_inter_item_corr) / (1 + (n_items - 1) *
10         mean_inter_item_corr)
11     return alpha
12
13 # Load the data
14 file_path = 'Likert_Scale_Data_for_SPSS.csv'
15 data = pd.read_csv(file_path)
16
17 # Split data by sections (adjust column ranges based on actual data)
18 experience_with_emi = data.iloc[:, 0:5]
19 language_skills_confidence = data.iloc[:, 5:10]
```

```

19
20 # Recalculate Cronbach's Alpha for each section and combined data
21 alpha_experience = calculate_cronbach_alpha(experience_with_emi)
22 alpha_skills_confidence = calculate_cronbach_alpha(language_skills_confidence)
23 alpha_combined = calculate_cronbach_alpha(data)
24
25 # Output results
26 print("Cronbach's Alpha_(Experience_with_EMI):", alpha_experience)
27 print("Cronbach's Alpha_(Language_Skills_and_Confidence):", alpha_skills_confidence
    )
28 print("Cronbach's Alpha_(Combined,_all_Likert-scale_items):", alpha_combined)

```

Listing A.1: Python script for calculating Cronbach’s Alpha

Output of the Code:

```

Cronbach's Alpha (Experience with EMI): 0.856649
Cronbach's Alpha (Language Skills and Confidence): 0.848005
Cronbach's Alpha (Combined, all Likert-scale items): 0.846533

```

A.1.2 Qualitative Data Analysis Table (NVivo 15)

Table A.1: Combined Theme Frequency and NVivo-Style Qualitative Data Analysis Table

Theme/Node	Coded Refer- ences/Frequency	Description/Sample Quotes
Student Comprehension and Comfort	12	Many students, especially from Bangla-medium backgrounds, struggle to follow lectures in English. They often fail to grasp terms or concepts explained in English.
Teacher Fluency and Comfort	10	Teachers face challenges due to lack of fluency in English, making them less confident when delivering lectures entirely in English.

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Theme/Node	Coded Refer- ences/Frequency	Description/Sample Quotes
Easier Understanding in Bangla	16	Students tend to understand lectures better when difficult concepts are explained in Bangla. Switching to Bangla provides clarity, especially for complex topics.
Exam-oriented Curriculum	9	The curriculum is heavily exam-focused, leading students to memorize content rather than understanding it deeply, especially when lectures are in English.
Mixed Method for Effectiveness	14	A mixed instructional method using both English and Bangla bridges the gap for students, improving comprehension and learning outcomes.
Classroom Language Practices	17	Language usage by teachers and students in EMI settings: Primarily in Bangla; English used when asking questions; Entirely in Bangla; Primarily in English; Entirely in English.
Student Challenges	15	Difficulties faced by students in adapting to EMI: 90% students are from Bangla medium, so they tend to struggle; Students cannot comprehend lectures delivered entirely in English; English is not their first language, adding pressure.
Teaching Challenges	10	Challenges faced by teachers in delivering EMI content: Lack of students' participation; Students have weak vocabulary; Teachers face difficulties due to diverse language levels among students.

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Theme/Node	Coded Refer- ences/Frequency	Description/Sample Quotes
Suggested Improve- ments	8	Recommendations for improving EMI: Make chunks of complex ideas and explain using simple terms; Regular practice and peer observation; Use multimedia aids and provide training.

Chapter B

Appendix

B.1 Consent Statement

By participating in this survey, you are agreeing to take part in a research study examining the experiences and perspectives of students enrolled in English-medium instruction (EMI) programs. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without penalty. Your responses will be kept strictly confidential and will be utilized solely for academic research purposes. No personally identifiable information will be disclosed. When we share results, responses will be anonymized so that no one can identify you.

Your honest feedback is greatly appreciated. It will help us understand the impact of English-medium instruction(EMI) and its associated challenges and identify areas for improvement. If you have any questions about this study, please feel free to contact the researchers before proceeding.

By clicking “Continue” or submitting your responses, you confirm that you understand what this research is about, voluntarily agree to participate, and consent to use the data you provide for the stated research purposes.

Chapter C

Appendix

C.1 Questionnaire

C.1.1 Student Questionnaire

1. Sample.
2. Discipline.
3. Gender.
4. Type of area where you completed your SSC.
5. Type of area where you completed your HSC.
6. Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?.
7. Study Year.
8. What was your first-year GPA?.
9. What is the last GPA result you've gained?.
10. How do your teachers conduct your class?.
11. How would you like your class to be conducted?.
12. Which class activity do you fear the most:.
13. How do you prepare yourself for exams:.

14. Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?.
15. I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.
16. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas.
17. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result.
18. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university.
19. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?.
20. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English.
21. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.
22. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.
23. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program.
24. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English (Listening Skill).
25. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty (Reading Skill).
26. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports (Writing Skill).
27. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant (Speaking Skill).
28. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?.
29. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?.
30. How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?.
31. Your Opinion on English-Medium Instruction (EMI) (Optional).

C.1.2 Teachers Questionnaire

1. Sample name.
2. Years teaching in English-medium instruction.
3. Medium of instruction in Teacher's undergraduate studies.
4. Self-rated English proficiency.
5. What language do you use for delivering class lectures?.
6. Comfort level delivering lectures completely in English.
7. What percentage of your students understand your lectures delivered in English?.
8. What challenges do you face delivering lectures in English?.
9. Have you received any training/support/education for English-medium instruction?.
10. What will help you teach more effectively in English?.
11. Why do you think teachers do not deliver their full class in English?.
12. How do you encourage student participation and engagement in English-medium classes?.
13. Do you receive feedback from students regarding their experience with English-medium instruction? If so, summarize common concerns or suggestions.
14. What suggestions do you have for teachers transitioning to English-medium instruction?.

C.1.3 Classroom Observation Criteria

1. Sample Name.
2. Language of Instruction.
3. Teaching Method.
4. Student Engagement.
5. Classroom Atmosphere.
6. Notable Interactions.

Chapter D

Appendix

D.1 Students' Responses (Sample)

1. **Sample:** STD1. **Discipline:** Science. **Gender:** Male. **Type of area where you completed your SSC:** Suburban area (Small Town). **Type of area where you completed your HSC:** Suburban area (Small Town). **Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?:** Bangla. **Study Year:** 1st Year. **Last GPA Result:** 3.1. **How do your teachers conduct your class?:** Bangla with a little English. **How would you like your class to be conducted?:** English with a little Bangla. **Which class activity do you fear the most?:** Class Test. **How do you prepare yourself for exams?:** Class Notes, Books, Internet, Senior's Notes. **Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?:** Sometimes. **I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.:** 2. **I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas:** 1. **I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result:** 2. **My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university:** 3. **Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?:** 3. **My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English:** 4. **During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.:** 2. **I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.:** 2. **I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program:** 3. **I can comfortably follow and understand**

lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 3. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 3. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 2. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 3. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 4. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: 90How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?: It's difficult for any Bangla Medium Student to perform well in semester exams. But EMI influencing a lot to perform well in exams as they can't avoid the exams no matter what. **Your Opinion on English-Medium Instruction (EMI) (Optional):** 1. it was during a lecture when i answered a question which was asked by the Course instructor. 2. During exam, i had to face challenges due to the shift to English Medium instruction. 3. I think when i try to fully understand academic books, specially books written by international author. 4. Don't avoid studying books written by international author. If any course instructor try to take the lesson fully in English, let them do. If u try to focus on the classes only, You'll fully understand the lecture. It'll be better if you join any English Language Club / Skills Developing Club.

2. **Sample:** STD2. **Discipline:** Business. **Gender:** Female. **Type of area where you completed your SSC:** Rural area (Village). **Type of area where you completed your HSC:** Urban area (Metropolitan/Big City). **Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?:** Bangla. **Study Year:** 2nd Year. **Last GPA Result:** . **How do your teachers conduct your class?:** English with a little Bangla. **How would you like your class to be conducted?:** English with a little Bangla. **Which class activity do you fear the most?:** Presentation. **How do you prepare yourself for exams?:** Books, Internet. **Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?:** Sometimes. **I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.:** 3. **I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas:** 4. **I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result:** 1. **My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university:** 4. **Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?:** 4. **My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if**

my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 4. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 4. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 4. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 4. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English.(Listening Skill): 4. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 4. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 4. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 2. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 3. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: A great amount of students can not get every topic if teacher talk totally in English. **How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?: Yes, it influences a lot. English becomes a habit for me and now I can understand barely enough to get topics that teachers discuss. I think this habit of listening, writing, reading and speaking in English will help me a lot to get opportunities.**

3. Sample: STD3. Discipline: Business. Gender: Female. Type of area where you completed your SSC: Suburban area (Small Town). Type of area where you completed your HSC: Suburban area (Small Town). Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?: Bangla. Study Year: Masters. What was your first-year GPA?: 3.16. Last GPA Result: 3.45. How do your teachers conduct your class?: Bangla with a little English. How would you like your class to be conducted?: Bangla with a little English. Which class activity do you fear the most:: Presentation. How do you prepare yourself for exams:: Internet, AI (e.g. Chat GPT). Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?: Yes, totally. I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.: 3. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas: 1. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result: 3. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university: 3. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?: 4. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the

full lesson in English: 3. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 4. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 2. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 4. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 3. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 2. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 2. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 2. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 3. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: All of the students don't know English properly. They might find it hard to understand. How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?: No influence. I just memorize and write them in the exam. Since the study is based on memorizing, so I just memorize and get a good score.

4. Sample: STD4. Discipline: Arts. Gender: Male. Type of area where you completed your SSC: Suburban area (Small Town). Type of area where you completed your HSC: Suburban area (Small Town). Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?: English. Study Year: 3rd Year. What was your first-year GPA?: 3.0. Last GPA Result: 3.25. How do your teachers conduct your class?: English with a little Bangla. How would you like your class to be conducted?: English with a little Bangla. Which class activity do you fear the most?: Presentation. How do you prepare yourself for exams?: Class Notes, Books, Internet, Senior's Notes. Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?: Sometimes. I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.: 3. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas: 3. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result: 2. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university: 4. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?: 4. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 4. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or

if I need to ask questions in English.: 4. **I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.:** 2. **I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program:** 4. **I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill):** 4. **I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill):** 4. **I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill):** 4. **I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill):** 3. **Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?:** 1. **Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?:** As all of us are not from the English medium, many words are unfamiliar to us and can't understand the whole lesson, for this reason teachers don't conduct their whole lesson in English, they try to make us understand full lesson and they use examples in native language sometime. **How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?:** I can improve my listening, speaking, reading in English and can be confidence in all of them, can make myself confident in seeking job opportunities, and so on.

5. Sample: STD5. **Discipline:** Arts. **Gender:** Male. **Type of area where you completed your SSC:** Suburban area (Small Town). **Type of area where you completed your HSC:** Suburban area (Small Town). **Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?:** Bangla. **Study Year:** 2nd Year. **What was your first-year GPA?:** 2.9. **Last GPA Result:** 3.1. **How do your teachers conduct your class?:** Bangla with a little English. **How would you like your class to be conducted?:** Bangla with a little English. **Which class activity do you fear the most::** Class Test. **How do you prepare yourself for exams::** Class Notes, Books, Internet, Senior's Notes. **Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?:** Sometimes. **I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.:** 3. **I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas:** 1. **I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result:** 2. **My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university:** 4. **Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?:** 4. **My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the**

full lesson in English: 2. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 1. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 4. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 3. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 2. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 2. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 2. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 3. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 1. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: As english is not their first language it puts an extra pressure to conduct the whole lecture in english. and it's easier for the students to understand the lecture. **How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?: Poor vocabulary is an issue. Sometimes I cannot write exactly what I'm thinking. That is a down side. **Your Opinion on English-Medium Instruction (EMI) (Optional):** Delivering a presentation in class was the first time I interacted with my class completely in English. Felt very nervous before the presentation. But after the presentation was successful I had a confidence boost.**

6. Sample: STD6. Discipline: Arts. Gender: Female. Type of area where you completed your SSC: Suburban area (Small Town). Type of area where you completed your HSC: Suburban area (Small Town). Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?: Bangla. Study Year: 2nd Year. What was your first-year GPA?: 3.05. Last GPA Result: 3.3. How do your teachers conduct your class?: Bangla with a little English. How would you like your class to be conducted?: Bangla with a little English. Which class activity do you fear the most?: Presentation. How do you prepare yourself for exams?: Class Notes. Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?: Sometimes. I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.: 3. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas: 2. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result: 1. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university: 3. Impact on academic performance since the transition to

English-medium instruction?: 4. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 3. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 4. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 4. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 3. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 3. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 3. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 3. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 2. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 3. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: As if students can understand easily. How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?: Slightly.

7. Sample: STD7. Discipline: Arts. Gender: Male. Type of area where you completed your SSC: Urban area (Metropolitan/Big City). Type of area where you completed your HSC: Urban area (Metropolitan/Big City). Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?: Bangla. Study Year: 1st Year. Last GPA Result: 2.85. How do your teachers conduct your class?: English with a little Bangla. How would you like your class to be conducted?: English with a little Bangla. Which class activity do you fear the most:: Presentation. How do you prepare yourself for exams:: Class Notes, AI (e.g. Chat GPT), Senior's Notes. Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?: Sometimes. I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.: 3. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas: 4. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result: 3. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university: 3. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?: 4. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 4. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 4. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 2. I feel

my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 2. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 4. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 4. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 4. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 2. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 4. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: As many of us from Bangla medium they think that we will not be able to understand the lesson if they take the class only in English.

8. Sample: STD8. Discipline: Arts. Gender: Female. Type of area where you completed your SSC: Rural area (Village). Type of area where you completed your HSC: Rural area (Village). Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?: Bangla. Study Year: 4th Year. What was your first-year GPA?: 3.0. Last GPA Result: 2.9. How do your teachers conduct your class?: English with a little Bangla. How would you like your class to be conducted?: English with a little Bangla. Which class activity do you fear the most?: Presentation. How do you prepare yourself for exams?: Class Notes, Books, Internet, Senior's Notes. Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?: Sometimes. I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.: 2. I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas: 2. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result: 2. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university: 4. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?: 4. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 2. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 1. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 1. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 4. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 4. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill):

3. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 3. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 3. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 1. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: As most of the students are not from English medium have a little proficiency in English, it becomes difficult to understand the class lectures when teachers conduct their whole lessons in English. I think that's the reason. **How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?:** As the instructions in exam questions are in English, one will try to learn at least basic sentences and vocabularies. I think that will increase their ability to understand any instructions provided in English.

9. Sample: STD9. Discipline: Arts. Gender: Female. Type of area where you completed your SSC: Rural area (Village). Type of area where you completed your HSC: Urban area (Metropolitan/Big City). Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?: Bangla. **Study Year: 3rd Year. What was your first-year GPA?:** 3.2. **Last GPA Result: 3.1. How do your teachers conduct your class?:** English with a little Bangla. **How would you like your class to be conducted?:** Totally in English. **Which class activity do you fear the most?:** Presentation. **How do you prepare yourself for exams?:** Class Notes, Books, Internet, Senior's Notes. **Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?:** Yes, totally. **I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.:** 3. **I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas: 2. I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result: 2. My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university: 3. Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?: 4. My English and understanding of your subject would be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 4. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.:** 4. **I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.:** 2. **I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 2. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 3. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant**

difficulty. (Reading Skill): 3. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 3. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 1. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 1. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: As most of the students came from bangla medium,si they sometimes face difficulties to understand the whole lecture in english.sometimes i think teachers don't feel comfortable to give lecture in English. They use little bit Bangla. **How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?:** It helps me to think every think in English, though i'm not that much goon in English. **Your Opinion on English-Medium Instruction (EMI) (Optional):** 1.when i see that every is also afraid of speaking English, they are also making mistakes,and students and teacher don't mock if anyone makes mistakes,then i feel comfortable. 2.At the beginning i face difficulties to understand the old English like Shakespeare's English, still facing problem.3.As I'm not fluent in English i face difficulties to memories and write answer in exam paper.4.I think teachers can play a significant rule to help students improving their English. Giving presentation frequently help students to over come their fear of speaking English.Active participation of students and teaches in language club can play a great role.

10. **Sample:** STD10. **Discipline:** Science. **Gender:** Male. **Type of area where you completed your SSC:** Suburban area (Small Town). **Type of area where you completed your HSC:** Suburban area (Small Town). **Have you studied any other curriculum apart from the national curriculum (Bangla)?:** Bangla. **Study Year:** 3rd Year. **What was your first-year GPA?:** 3.05. **Last GPA Result:** 2.95. **How do your teachers conduct your class?:** Bangla with a little English. **How would you like your class to be conducted?:** Totally in English. **Which class activity do you fear the most::** Presentation. **How do you prepare yourself for exams::** Internet, YouTube. **Do you consult previous year questions when preparing for exams?:** Sometimes. **I rely on memorizing past questions and suggestions for exam.:** 3. **I focus on understanding and writing answers using my own ideas:** 2. **I think studying previous year questions can help one gain a decent result:** 2. **My overall experience with English-medium instruction at the university:** 3. **Impact on academic performance since the transition to English-medium instruction?:** 4. **My English and understanding of your subject would**

be much better if my teachers could take the full lesson in English: 3. During class, I feel anxious when asked to express my ideas or if I need to ask questions in English.: 4. I am confident in seeking job opportunities that require strong English language skills.: 2. I feel my English communication skills (speaking, writing, reading, listening) have improved significantly since starting your program: 3. I can comfortably follow and understand lectures delivered entirely in English. (Listening Skill): 2. I can read and understand academic texts written in English without significant difficulty. (Reading Skill): 2. I feel confident expressing my ideas in written English for assignments and reports. (writing Skill): 2. I can actively participate in class discussions and presentations in English without feeling overly hesitant. (Speaking Skill): 1. Do you believe that the GED (English) course is sufficient for building English skill?: 3. Why do you think teachers do not conduct their whole lesson in English?: As most of us are from bangla medium,they tend to teach in bangla to make us comfortable in order to understand. How is EMI (English medium instruction) influencing your overall performance in exam?: My sentence making skill is getting better.

D.2 Teachers' Responses (Sample)

1. Sample name: T01 Years teaching in English-medium instruction: 2.0 Undergraduate Instruction Medium: Bangla Self-rated English proficiency: 4 What language do you use for delivering class lectures?: Mostly Bangla with a little English Comfort level delivering lectures completely in English: 3 What percentage of your students understand your lectures delivered in English?: 0.5 What challenges do you face delivering lectures in English?: Lack of students participation in classroom interaction.l Have you received any training/support/education for English-medium instruction?: No What will help you teach more effectively in English?: Using multimodal classroom settings may help. Why do you think teachers do not deliver their full class in English?: For comprehension of the students and lack of practice. How do you encourage student participation and engagement in English-medium classes?: I ask question and repeat after them Do you receive feedback from students regarding their experience with English-medium instruction? If so, summarize common concerns or suggestions.: For any new theory or term it helps the most students effectively if it is explained in their first language. What suggestions do you have for teachers

transitioning to English-medium instruction?: Make chunks of complex ideas and explain using easy and known synonym while introducing a new topic. The knowledge itself matters, not necessarily medium.

2. **Sample name:** T02 Years teaching in English-medium instruction: 20.0 Undergraduate Instruction Medium: English **Self-rated English proficiency:** 3 **What language do you use for delivering class lectures?:** Mostly Bangla with a little English **Comfort level delivering lectures completely in English:** 4 **What percentage of your students understand your lectures delivered in English?:** 0.7 **What challenges do you face delivering lectures in English?:** Some students have poor language comprehension skill. **Have you received any training/support/education for English-medium instruction?:** No **What will help you teach more effectively in English?:** Use of visual aids/multimedia may help to teach more effectively in English. **Why do you think teachers do not deliver their full class in English?:** While one very obvious reason for not delivering a full class in English is the student's lack of English comprehension skill, there are other issues like teacher's incapability to conduct a full session in English, and also, the teacher's propensity/inclination to reduce the cognitive load of processing L2 when they are delivering the lecture or giving instructions on the class. **How do you encourage student participation and engagement in English-medium classes?:** As I teach courses of language and linguistics, in my class I encourage my students to share their experience in the classroom and cite real life examples related to the topic. **Do you receive feedback from students regarding their experience with English-medium instruction? If so, summarize common concerns or suggestions.:** Because some students fail to comprehend a good portion of the lecture in English due to their poor comprehension skill, sometimes there are requests to explain the concepts in Bangla (L1). Sometimes the technical terms and language of the textbooks are very difficult for them and they are unable to make a relation between the lectures and the text. A simplified handout could be helpful for the students. **What suggestions do you have for teachers transitioning to English-medium instruction?:** I suggest that one should try to hone their linguistic skills first, either through in person training or using online platforms. Besides, they would need to develop classroom management skill. It would be great if they can make a survey among the students at the beginning of the course to get an idea of the students' English language comprehension level which would help them to decide what

strategies they should apply in the class to make the lectures comprehensible for the students.

3. Sample name: T03 **Years teaching in English-medium instruction:** 14.5 **Undergraduate Instruction Medium:** English **Self-rated English proficiency:** 4 **What language do you use for delivering class lectures?:** Mostly English with a little Bangla **Comfort level delivering lectures completely in English:** 4 **What percentage of your students understand your lectures delivered in English?:** 0.7 **What challenges do you face delivering lectures in English?:** The background and the levels of the students; different types of attitudes, aptitudes and approaches of the learners; classroom size. **Have you received any training/support/education for English-medium instruction?:** Yes **What will help you teach more effectively in English?:** small groups of learners with personal motivations; getting students to interact in the classroom; authentic texts, access to research and information. **Why do you think teachers do not deliver their full class in English?:** Teachers are not fluent in English themselves; to balance the different types of learners coming from different backgrounds with language variations. **How do you encourage student participation and engagement in English-medium classes?:** Make the students understanding the language itself; group work; pair work; assimilating the native language and the target language and submersion teaching. **Do you receive feedback from students regarding their experience with English-medium instruction? If so, summarize common concerns or suggestions.:** No **What suggestions do you have for teachers transitioning to English-medium instruction?:** They should teach in English relinquishing the native language for the time being. They should teach in English keeping in mind the academic purposes and the educational policies and values and to bring a social change.

4. Sample name: T04 **Years teaching in English-medium instruction:** 11.0 **Undergraduate Instruction Medium:** Bangla **Self-rated English proficiency:** 3 **What language do you use for delivering class lectures?:** Mostly Bangla with a little English **Comfort level delivering lectures completely in English:** 3 **What percentage of your students understand your lectures delivered in English?:** 0.5 **What challenges do you face delivering lectures in English?:** Since I am a native Bangla speaker, I don't have much proficiency, confidence, or comfort to deliver a full class in English. Sometimes, I find it easier to make students understand topics in Bangla. **Have you received any training/support/education for English-medium instruction?:** No **What will help you teach more effectively in English?:** 1. Proper training

and regular practice. 2. Adequate options to promote speaking skills. 3. Using technology (e.g., ChatGPT, YouTube). **Why do you think teachers do not deliver their full class in English?:** Most of the teachers' mother tongue is Bangla. Thus, they lack confidence and comfort in delivering lectures in English. They don't receive proper training in conducting English-medium classes. Our education system focuses on reading and writing skills over speaking and conversational skills. **How do you encourage student participation and engagement in English-medium classes?:** 1. by improving teacher's speaking conversational skill 2. by enhancing teacher's self confidence 3. by making students comfortable in using English **Do you receive feedback from students regarding their experience with English-medium instruction? If so, summarize common concerns or suggestions.:** No, I haven't received feedback. Our administrative system doesn't facilitate gathering feedback from students. **What suggestions do you have for teachers transitioning to English-medium instruction?:** 1. Get professional English training. 2. Self-motivation and self-development.

D.3 Classroom Observation Report (Sample)

1. **Teacher:** Teacher 1 **Language of Instruction:** Primarily in Bangla; English used when asking students to read. **Teaching Method:** Traditional reading and translation. No group activities or multimedia tools. **Student Engagement:** Students appeared disengaged and passive; little interaction observed. **Classroom Atmosphere:** Distant and formal. Lacked a lively, interactive environment. **Notable Interactions:** No extraordinary moments observed.

2. **Teacher:** Teacher 2 **Language of Instruction:** Primarily in English; occasionally uses Bangla for real-life explanations or upon student request. **Teaching Method:** Interactive with group work, assignments, and fieldwork. Focus on enhancing writing skills. **Student Engagement:** Highly interactive and engaging. Students actively participate and ask questions in English. **Classroom Atmosphere:** Balanced between formal and friendly. Encourages active participation. **Notable Interactions:** Used fieldwork to enhance student skills; notable integration of technology like Google Forms.

3. **Teacher:** Teacher 3 **Language of Instruction:** Entirely in Bangla; uses English only to read from a book and then explains in Bangla. **Teaching Method:** Reads from books and explains in Bangla. No group activities or multimedia tools. **Student Engagement:** Students

were attentive due to subject interest but interacted entirely in Bangla. **Classroom Atmosphere:** Friendly and interactive. Teacher knows students by name and fosters rapport. **Notable Interactions:** Contradiction between interview and observation; claimed to teach in English but entirely in Bangla.

4. **Teacher:** Teacher 4 **Language of Instruction:** Entirely in English; occasionally uses Bangla upon request. **Teaching Method:** Uses projector slides; assigns group work, presentations, and fieldwork. Collects feedback via Google Forms. **Student Engagement:** Students participate but occasionally lose attention due to heavy reliance on slides. **Classroom Atmosphere:** Friendly environment with effective use of group work and feedback. **Notable Interactions:** Incorporated real-life references relevant to Bangladesh; used Google Forms for feedback.